

Antarctic Ecosystem Inventory:

Descriptive profiles for Ice-free lands v1.01

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Introduction

The Antarctic Ecosystem Inventory includes a hierarchical classification and maps for ice-free lands of Antarctica developed using methods described by Tóth et al. (2024). The purposes of the inventory are to support i) policy and management planning for biodiversity conservation under the Montreal Protocol of the Antarctic Treaty; and ii) the advance of ecological knowledge of Antarctic ecosystems and component biota. The classification includes three tiers. **Major environmental units** (Tier 1) represent major variations in environmental, climatic, and topographic conditions across the continent. **Habitat complexes** (Tier 2) represent locally significant variations in the combined habitat suitability for a range of vertebrate, invertebrate, plant and other taxa. **Bioregional ecosystem types** (Tier 3) represent regional variants of Habitat complexes occurring in different Antarctic Conservation Biogeographic Regions (ACBRs), consistent with Level 4 units in the IUCN Global Ecosystem Typology (Keith *et al.*, 2022). This level of classification serves as a proxy for regional turnover (gamma diversity) of biota. This data record includes descriptive profiles for the units in each tier of classification and accompanies a data record including the spatial data and the Data Descriptor (Tóth et al. 2024).

Major Environmental Units

Nine major environmental units are recognized in Tier 1 of the Antarctic ecosystem typology v1.0, including five from the factor analysis (encoded E1-E5) and four specialised ecosystem units (G1-G3 geothermal ecosystems and L1 lakes) mapped through separate work flows (Tóth et al. 2024). Each of the units from this factor analysis is subdivided into 4-7 Habitat Complexes determined by a second factor analysis based on habitat suitability data, each designated by a unique identifier comprising the environmental unit code and a habitat code preceded by “B” within each unit (e.g. E3B1 for the first habitat in the environmental unit E3). E1B8 penguin colonies were added as a specialised Habitat Complex within the mild lowlands unit based on a separate workflow (E1B8). The three specialised ecosystem units recognized at Tier 1 were not further subdivided into Habitat Complexes.). Table 1 summarises the key features of these units, while the visualisations display their environmental relationships in relation to environmental gradients.

Table 1. Characteristics of Major environmental units (Tier 1).

Major Environmental Group	Distribution	Description
E1 Mild lowlands	Throughout coastal areas of Antarctica with particular concentrations on the Antarctic Peninsula, the coastal fringe of Transantarctic Mountains, and Victoria Land. Dominates the coastal outcrops around the eastern margin of the continent.	Relatively warm, flat/level habitats, often coastal but not always. Elevations are low and topography is gentle. May be rocky and barren, but often hosts bird colonies and pinnipeds if occurring near the coast.
E2 Midland humid habitats	Dominates mountainous areas of the Antarctic Peninsula, with strong	Occurs on a variety of terrain types at low-to-mid elevations, usually near

Major Environmental Group	Distribution	Description
	representation in the Transantarctic mountains and Victoria Land. E2B1 and E2B2 are concentrated on the Peninsula, while E2B3 and E2B4 are found all around the continent including on the (mainly southern) Peninsula, particularly where colder and drier conditions intersect with snowy and cloudy midland terrain.	the coast. Characterised by high cloud cover, snowfall and relatively high temperatures because of low elevation. Thick snow cover (probably seasonal) remains on the surfaces, which are generally not steep enough for the snow to slide down. Bryophytes and lichens comprise a substantial portion of the terrestrial biota.
E3 Midland dry/sunny habitats	Occurs all over Antarctica with good representation, but particularly dominant in Victoria Land	Sunlit (north-facing) rocky slopes with low snow cover that may vary from low to high elevation and relatively gentle to steep grades.
E4 High mountains	Occurs sprinkled among other ecosystems where steep slopes are present. E4B1 and E4B6 occur patchily on rugged areas of the Peninsula, and all subunits occur in the Transantarctic Mountains.	High elevation, extremely cold, arid, and rugged ecosystems receiving low levels of solar radiation. Slopes are too steep to hold a permanent snow layer and are typically barren rock with very little biota. Habitats have little or no growing season.
E5 High flatlands	Occurs throughout the main continent but is absent from the Antarctic Peninsula	Cold and arid high-elevation flatlands and plateaus with low cloud cover. Characterised especially by high winds.
G1-3 Geothermal areas	Representation in the northern Antarctic Peninsula, Marie Byrd and Enderby Lands, Victoria Land, and East Antarctica	Areas where geothermal processes influence the environment or biota of ecosystems either directly or historically.
L Lakes	Current knowledge about the distribution of Antarctic lakes is incomplete; however, over 1,300 terrestrial lakes have been mapped in ice-free areas. Hundreds of lakes ranging from a few metres to a few kilometres across are dotted across the McMurdo Dry Valleys and North Victoria Land. Lakes are also documented in Marie Byrd Land, Dronning Maud Land, Enderby Land, the Prince Charles Mountains, East Antarctica, the Antarctic Peninsula, and the Transantarctic Mountains. Some local areas, such as the Vestfold Hills and the Larsemann Hills, have notably high concentrations of lakes.	Surface lakes range from small ponds to kettle lakes and large lake systems. They occur where meltwater drainage pathways flow from snowfields, glaciers, the ice sheet and permafrost into basins or depressions (including on glaciers and ice sheets) and are often spatially isolated. Conditions range from frozen solid to their bases in winter to seasonally ice covered, losing surface ice cover for a few weeks to months in summer, with some lakes being ice free year round due to their salinity.

Figure 1. A visual overview of the classification of Major Environmental Units. Cloud, melt, and totPrecip are moisture availability variables. MeanTemp is the mean Temperature in 2014-2015 and DDM5 is the degree-days over -5 degrees centigrade, a common measure of the growing season. Solar is solar radiation, calculated from aspect, reflected light, and other factors. Elevation, rugosity and slope are terrain variables based on the digital elevation model (Table S1); and wind is an average measure of wind speed.

A visual overview of the spatial distribution and environmental and biotic properties for each Habitat Complex is given below. Each Major Environmental Unit has three figures, (A) a map, (B) boxplots of abiotic variables and (C) boxplots of habitat suitability variables.

Spatial statistics showing representation of the Habitat Complexes among Antarctic Conservation Biogeographic Regions.

Figure 2. Distribution of unit areas among Antarctic Conservation Bioregions (ACBRs); areas less than 50 km² are not shown. Penguin colonies are not shown as they have less than 50 km² of area in all ACBRs.

Figure 7. Distribution of unit areas among ACBRs as a proportion of total area; habitat complexes comprising less than 5% of an ACBR’s area are not shown. Relative sizes of the bubbles indicate proportion and give an idea of the evenness of Habitat Complexes in each ACBR. Larger bubbles therefore indicate that an ACBR is dominated by one or a few Habitat Complexes.

Environmental group E1 (Mild lowlands)

A.

B.

C.

Environmental group E2 (Midland mesic habitats)

A.

B.

C.

Environmental group E3 (Midland dry/sunny habitats)

A.

B.

C.

Environmental group E4 (Rugged high mountains)

A.

B.

C.

Environmental group E5 (Highland windy plateaus)

A.

B.

C.

Environmental groups G1-G3 & L1 (Geothermal Areas and Lakes)

A.

B.

C.

Habitat Complexes

This section contains detailed profiles at the Tier 2 level (Habitat Complexes). The profiles bring together information from satellite imagery, the biotic and abiotic data that forms the basis of the classification, and a database of Antarctic flora and fauna including spatial locations of samples.

Within Major Environmental Units, Habitat Complexes exhibit stronger differentiation along gradients related to total precipitation, length of growing season and cloud cover than along other gradients (Figs. 2-5), although exposure to high winds is an important distinguishing factor in E1 mild lowlands and E3 midland dry sunny environments (Fig. 4).

Figure 2. Terrain-related variables for Major Environmental Units (panels) and Habitat Complex (ellipses), represented as 50% confidence ellipses. The legend indicates the color of each Habitat Complex; i.e. the yellow ellipse in panel E1 represents Habitat Complex E1B4.

Figure 3. Moisture availability-related variables for Major Environmental Units (panels) and Habitat Complex (ellipses), represented as 50% confidence ellipses. Note the logged axes.

Figure 4. Wind and light conditions for Major Environmental Units (panels) and Habitat Complex (ellipses), represented as 50% confidence ellipses. Note the logged axes.

Figure 5. Cloud and growing season (DDm5) for Major Environmental Units (panels) and Habitat Complex (ellipses), represented as 50% confidence ellipses. Note the logged axes. Cloud and growing season

Terminology

The Antarctic Conservation Biogeographic Regions (ACBRs) are referred to by name throughout much of the document, while the term “Antarctic Peninsula” or simply “the Peninsula” is used to refer to ACBRs 1, 3, 4, and 15 collectively. The term “Victoria Land” is used to refer to North and South Victoria Land collectively.

In the “Biota” section of each profile, a table summarises the species most widely sampled in the Habitat Complex. In this table, the “Antarctic Specialist” column indicates whether GBIF records of the species included samples north of -50 degrees of latitude. If so, this field is FALSE, and if not, then the field is TRUE. The column “count” refers to how many cells the species was sampled in based on records held in Terauds et al. (2023b), and the “percent of samples” column refers to the count divided by the sum of counts over the complete table (i.e., pixels are counted multiple times if multiple species were sampled in them).

See Table 1 in Toth et al. (2024) for a summary of all variables that are included in the figures in this document. Abbreviated variable names are: totPrecip = total annual

precipitation; DDm5 = degree-days above -5 degrees centigrade; meanTemp is the mean annual temperature.

MAJOR ENVIRONMENTAL UNIT E1

Major Environmental Unit E1 is, on average, substantially higher in DDm5, meanTemp and melt than continental Antarctica. It is substantially lower in elevation, rugosity, slope and totPrecip than the rest of the continent.

Major Environmental Unit E1 is, on average, substantially higher in suitability for Bacidiacid, Candelarid, and Cladonid lichens, Mesostigmatid, and Trombidiformes mites, Bryales, Dicranales, Hypnales, and Polytrichales mosses, and Chinstrap and Gentoo penguins than the rest of Antarctica. It is not substantially lower in suitability for any functional groups than the rest of the continent.

Habitat Complex E1B1: *Mild coastal inclines and beaches*

Rocky, gently sloping lowlands in warm, cloudy mesic (high snowfall) areas; has seasonal snow cover and usually exhibits meltwater erosion channels. This unit supports a rich biota dominated mainly by lichens, mosses and seabirds. Colonies of penguins on the coast and nesting seabirds influence moss beds upslope enriched by nutrients via updrafts. Antarctic hair grass (*Deschampsia antarctica*) occurs occasionally within this system at low elevations on the Antarctic Peninsula and associated islands, but not in other areas. The microbiota is likely to exhibit strong regional variation within this unit around the continent. Based on sampling, these areas appear to be the most favoured ecosystem for several species of seabirds (terns, gulls, skuas), mosses, mites, and springtails. A favoured nesting environment on the Peninsula for the southern giant petrel, which has been sampled in large numbers. This unit has the highest sampling of 102 relatively common species (at least 10 occurrences), and 20 of these are found in this unit for more than 50% of their samples.

Photographic images

Distribution

Occurs mainly in the coastal Antarctic Peninsula and Marie Byrd Land. Very common on beaches of coastal islands off the Peninsula. Minor occurrences on the coast of the Transantarctic Mountains and East Antarctica.

Environment

The Habitat Complex E1B1 is part of the Major Environmental Unit E1.

The elevation of E1B1 ranges from 0 to 1480 metres above sea level, but 90% of its pixels fall above 5 and below 706 metres. Its median elevation is 125 metres.

The Habitat Complex is higher in DDm5, cloud, meanTemp, totPrecip and wind and lower in elevation than the rest of Major Environmental Unit E1.

Comparison of environmental properties of this Habitat Complex with those of its Major Environmental Unit and the entire ice-free area of Antarctica

Biota

Most widely sampled species in E1B1 (found in most pixels)

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Pygoscelis adeliae</i>	Chordata_Aves_Sphenisciformes_Spheniscidae_Pygoscelis_adeliae	Chordata	FALSE	39	1.63
<i>Polytrichastrum alpinum</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Polytrichales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	38	1.59
<i>Bryum pseudotriquetrum</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Bryales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	35	1.46
<i>Cryptopygus antarcticus</i>	Arthropoda_Entognatha_Entomobryomorpha__	Arthropoda	TRUE	35	1.46
<i>Larus dominicanus</i>	Chordata_Aves_Charadriiformes__	Chordata	TRUE	32	1.34
<i>Pygoscelis antarctica</i>	Chordata_Aves_Sphenisciformes_Spheniscidae_Pygoscelis_antarctica	Chordata	TRUE	32	1.34
<i>Ceratodon purpureus</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Dicranales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	30	1.25
<i>Friesea grisea</i>	Arthropoda_Entognatha_Poduromorpha__	Arthropoda	FALSE	28	1.17
<i>Sanionia uncinata</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Hypnales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	28	1.17

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Pygoscelis papua</i>	Chordata_Aves_Sphenisciformes_Spheniscidae_Pygoscelis_papua	Chordata	FALSE	26	1.09
<i>Usnea aurantiaco-atra</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae_	Ascomycota	FALSE	26	1.09

Distinctiveness of the unit from the Major Environmental Unit and the rest of Antarctica

Habitat Complex E1B2: Meltwater-eroded flatlands

Rocky, gently sloping lowlands characterised by high seasonal melt and meltwater erosion, creating a complex, dynamic terrestrial surface, and higher rugosity than is usual for the group. Satellite imagery suggests a layer of loose, crumbling soils in some areas. Common mosses and lichens are its dominant biota, but the unit may host chinstrap penguin

colonies. Sampled biota includes a number of cyanobacteria and Ochrophyte species that are apparently unique to this habitat.

Photographic images

Distribution

Occurs mainly on the Antarctic Peninsula, but a scattering of this unit can also be found coastally in the Transantarctic Mountains, Victoria Land, Marie Byrd Land. There is a patch of this Habitat Complex in the Bunger Hills, East Antarctica.

Environment

The Habitat Complex E1B2 is part of the Major Environmental Unit E1.

The elevation of E1B2 ranges from 0 to 1278 metres above sea level, but 90% of its pixels fall above 20 and below 737 metres. Its median elevation is 275 metres.

The Habitat Complex is higher in melt, rugosity, slope and totPrecip and lower in no variables than the rest of Major Environmental Unit E1.

Comparison of environmental properties of this Habitat Complex with those of its Major Environmental Unit and the entire ice-free area of Antarctica

Biota

Most widely sampled species in E1B2 (found in most pixels)

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Usnea sphacelata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	13	3.17
<i>Pseudophebe minuscula</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	12	2.93
<i>Umbilicaria decussata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Umbilicariales_Umbilicariaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	12	2.93
<i>Ceratodon purpureus</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Dicranales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	10	2.44
<i>Bryum pseudotriquetrum</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Bryales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	9	2.20
<i>Schistidium antarctici</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Grimmiales__	Bryophyta	TRUE	9	2.20
<i>Usnea antarctica</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	8	1.95
<i>Bryum argenteum</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Bryales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	7	1.71
<i>Physcia caesia</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloscistiales_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	7	1.71
<i>Bryum amblyodon</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Bryales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	6	1.46

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Buellia grisea</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloschistales_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	6	1.46
<i>Rhizocarpon geographicum</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Not assigned_Rhizocarpaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	6	1.46
<i>Umbilicaria aprina</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Umbilicariales_Umbilicariaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	6	1.46

Distinctiveness of the unit from the Major Environmental Unit and the rest of Antarctica

Habitat Complex E1B3: Xeric valley floors

Sloped or rolling valley sides or low outcrops in valleys typically carved by antecedent glaciers and transitioning to steeper cliffs and high peaks. The valleys may extend many kilometres inland and are strongly sheltered from the wind and sun and are extremely dry. Some incidence of this unit is also seen between the edge of existing glaciers and steeper mountain slopes. These systems are colder than the rest of the lowlands, but still warmer than the continental average. The vegetation is sparse due to extremely dry conditions, characterised mainly by Lecanorid and Teloschistid lichens with high suitability for

Stereocaulid lichens, nematodes, trombidiformid mites, rotifers, green algae, and springtails. Highly characteristic moss *Encaplypta procera* found primarily in this habitat.

Photographic images

Ecosystem complex on Alexander Island; snapshot from Google Earth pro.

Bull Pass, McMurdo Dry valleys

Distribution

Occurs primarily in South Victoria Land (particularly the McMurdo Dry Valleys area). Minor occurrences also exist on the northern shore of Alexander Island, in Dronning Maud Land and the Transantarctic Mountains.

Environment

The Habitat Complex E1B3 is part of the Major Environmental Unit E1.

The elevation of E1B3 ranges from 0 to 1866 metres above sea level, but 90% of its pixels fall above 64 and below 925 metres. Its median elevation is 458 metres.

The Habitat Complex is higher in elevation and melt and lower in DDm5, totPrecip and wind than the rest of Major Environmental Unit E1.

Comparison of environmental properties of this Habitat Complex with those of its Major Environmental Unit and the entire ice-free area of Antarctica

Biota

Most widely sampled species in E1B3 (found in most pixels)

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Gomphiocephalus hodgsoni</i>	Arthropoda_Entognatha_Poduro-morpha__	Arthropoda	TRUE	34	2.87
<i>Usnea sphacelata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	24	2.02
<i>Stereotydeus mollis</i>	Arthropoda_Arachnida_Trombidiformes__	Arthropoda	TRUE	22	1.85
<i>Scottinema lindsayae</i>	Nematoda__	Nematoda	TRUE	20	1.69
<i>Encalypta procera</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Pottiales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	19	1.60
<i>Eudorylaimus antarcticus</i>	Nematoda__	Nematoda	TRUE	18	1.52

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Bryum pseudotriquetrum</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Bryales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	17	1.43
<i>Friesea topo</i>	Arthropoda_Entognatha_Poduromorphaha__	Arthropoda	TRUE	13	1.10
<i>Distichium capillaceum</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Dicranales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	12	1.01
<i>Syntrichia princeps</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Pottiales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	12	1.01

Distinctiveness of the unit from the Major Environmental Unit and the rest of Antarctica

Habitat Complex E1B4: Exposed rocky flatlands

Cold despite low elevations, little snowfall but often contains lakes maintained by meltwater streams. Terrain is especially low and flat. Wind tends to be high as this unit is not sheltered by topographic features. Samples comprise mainly lichens and mosses, and also several species of diatoms. Suitability is high for lichens in the families

Acarosporaceae, Parmeliaceae and Lecanoraceae. An unusual number of algae, green algae, and cyanobacteria species are attributed to this habitat, however, this is likely due to extensive sampling in and around lakes that are often found in this habitat.

Photographic images

Distribution

Occurs mainly in the Transantarctic Mountains and Victoria Land with a scattering of sites in Marie Byrd Land, Enderby Land, and the Prince Charles Mountains. Notably, the Vestfold Hills of East Antarctica are primarily composed of this habitat.

Environment

The Habitat Complex E1B4 is part of the Major Environmental Unit E1.

The elevation of E1B4 ranges from 0 to 1741 metres above sea level, but 90% of its pixels fall above 6 and below 617 metres. Its median elevation is 159 metres.

The Habitat Complex is higher in wind and lower in DDM5, elevation, rugosity, slope and totPrecip than the rest of Major Environmental Unit E1.

Comparison of environmental properties of this Habitat Complex with those of its Major Environmental Unit and the entire ice-free area of Antarctica

Biota

Most widely sampled species in E1B4 (found in most pixels)

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Bryum pseudotriquetrum</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Bryales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	67	3.51
<i>Buellia frigida</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Telosc histaes_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	47	2.46
<i>Umbilicaria aprina</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Umbil icariales_Umbilicariaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	36	1.88
<i>Ceratodon purpureus</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Dicranales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	35	1.83
<i>Rhizoplaca melanophthalma</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecan orales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	34	1.78
<i>Acarospora gwynnii</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Acaro sporales_Acarosporaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	32	1.68
<i>Caloplaca citrina</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Telosc histaes_Teloschistaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	32	1.68
<i>Candelariella flava</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Cande lariales_Candelariaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	30	1.57
<i>Lecanora expectans</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecan orales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	28	1.47
<i>Chaetoceros sp.</i>	Ochrophyta__	Ochrophyta	TRUE	27	1.41

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Navicula salinarum</i>	Ochrophyta____	Ochrophyta	FALSE	27	1.41

Distinctiveness of the unit from the Major Environmental Unit and the rest of Antarctica

Habitat Complex E1B5: Subcoastal exposed mossy outcrops

These mossy ecosystems occupy low-relief rocky outcrops in the sub-coastal hinterlands or directly on the coastline. Conditions are sufficiently warm and sunny to promote moss growth, but windier than other coastal systems in E1, leading to presence of aeolian (wind-eroded) contours. Several processes are likely to enhance habitat suitability for mosses by promoting nutrient enrichment. Many occurrences coincide with current or abandoned penguin colonies that were active earlier in the Holocene when sea levels were higher than at present. Toxic nitrogen levels associated with previously active colonies have since been leached, while residual levels of N and other nutrients promote moss growth. Alternatively, more elevated sites receive nutrient influxes from nesting seabirds or aerosol inputs via

updrafts from extant penguin colonies below. While mosses are often conspicuous features of these systems, lichens and some nematodes are also widespread; they are popular with snow petrels, Wilson's storm petrels, and several cyanobacteria species are characteristic of occurrences in different regions of the continent. A number of moss and lichen species that are common across many ecosystems are nonetheless most common in this habitat.

Photographic images

Distribution

Dominates Adélie Land, Enderby Land and East Antarctica, with patchy occurrences found coastally scattered around the western side of the continent.

Environment

The Habitat Complex E1B5 is part of the Major Environmental Unit E1.

The elevation of E1B5 ranges from 0 to 1712 metres above sea level, but 90% of its pixels fall above 8 and below 787 metres. Its median elevation is 214 metres.

The Habitat Complex is higher in wind and lower in melt, rugosity and slope than the rest of Major Environmental Unit E1.

Comparison of environmental properties of this Habitat Complex with those of its Major Environmental Unit and the entire ice-free area of Antarctica

Biota

Most widely sampled species in E1B5 (found in most pixels)

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Ceratodon purpureus</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Dicranales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	70	3.38
<i>Umbilicaria decussata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Umbilicariales_Umbilicariaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	67	3.24
<i>Bryum pseudotriquetrum</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Bryales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	60	2.90
<i>Pagodroma nivea</i>	Chordata_Aves_Procellariiformes__	Chordata	FALSE	59	2.85
<i>Buellia frigida</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloschistales_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	51	2.46
<i>Oceanites oceanicus</i>	Chordata_Aves_Procellariiformes__	Chordata	TRUE	44	2.13
<i>Usnea sphacelata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	42	2.03
<i>Usnea antarctica</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	40	1.93
<i>Candelariella flava</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Candelariales_Candelariaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	39	1.88
<i>Pseudephebe minuscula</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	36	1.74

Distinctiveness of the unit from the Major Environmental Unit and the rest of Antarctica

Habitat Complex E1B6: *Glacial outwash plains*

Located primarily at the terminus of glaciers, outwash plains contain debris and sediment from meltwater outflow that is often sorted by size, with larger rocks and boulders nearer to the glacier and smaller particles such as silt farther away. In Taylor Valley, by far the largest continuous incidence of this uncommon habitat, the outwash plain is a part of the Ross Sea 1 Drift (Perotti et al. 2018, Hawes et al. 2021) and contains a variety of interbedded substrates including gravel, silt, and sand. The habitat often contains an abundance of kettle lakes and may be crisscrossed by meltwater streams.

Photographic images

Habitat Complex E1B6 at the mouth of Taylor Valley

The Price Charles Mountains – snapshot from Google Earth Pro

Distribution

Aside from patchy relatively minor occurrences (< 100 km² per bioregion) in the Antarctic Peninsula, the Transantarctic Mountains, Enderby Land and the Prince Charles Mountains,

this habitat is found primarily in Victoria Land, particularly in the McMurdo dry valleys (~800 km²), which constitutes over half of its total area.

Environment

The Habitat Complex E1B6 is part of the Major Environmental Unit E1.

The elevation of E1B6 ranges from 0 to 1992 metres above sea level, but 90% of its pixels fall above 0 and below 946 metres. Its median elevation is 248 metres.

The Habitat Complex is higher in no variables and lower in melt than the rest of Major Environmental Unit E1.

Comparison of environmental properties of this Habitat Complex with those of its Major Environmental Unit and the entire ice-free area of Antarctica

Biota

Most widely sampled species in E1B6 (found in most pixels)

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Gomphiocephalus hodgsoni</i>	Arthropoda_Entognatha_Poduroomorpha__	Arthropoda	TRUE	44	2.37
<i>Stereotydeus mollis</i>	Arthropoda_Arachnida_Trombidiformes__	Arthropoda	TRUE	41	2.21
<i>Bryum pseudotriquetrum</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Bryales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	35	1.89
<i>Scottinema lindsayae</i>	Nematoda__	Nematoda	TRUE	31	1.67
<i>Buellia frigida</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloschistales_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	30	1.62
<i>Eudorylaimus antarcticus</i>	Nematoda__	Nematoda	TRUE	28	1.51
<i>Xanthoria elegans</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloschistales_Teloschistaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	26	1.40
<i>Plectus murrayi</i>	Nematoda__	Nematoda	TRUE	23	1.24
<i>Ceratodon purpureus</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Dicranales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	21	1.13
<i>Umbilicaria decussata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Umbilicariales_Umbilicariaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	21	1.13

Distinctiveness of the unit from the Major Environmental Unit and the rest of Antarctica

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Habitat Complex E1B7: *Dry lowland lichen fields*

Primarily occurs on flat, rocky terrain or low outcrops on cold, dry and windy coastlines (though there are occasional occurrences inland), commonly (but not exclusively) adjacent to ice shelves. Characteristic biota includes several common moss and lichen recorded primarily from this unit. Nutrient fluxes potentially influenced by emperor penguin colonies on adjacent ice shelves. Suitability is high for all functional groups. Several

otherwise unusual species of lichens have been sampled most frequently in this habitat, including several Teloschistaceae (genus *Caloplaca*) and Lecanoraceae.

Photographic images

Distribution

Patchy occurrences around much of Antarctica. Found most commonly in the Transantarctic Mountains Victoria Land but there is also a notable concentration of this habitat on James Ross Island and minor patches in the Ellsworth and Prince Charles Mountains.

Environment

The Habitat Complex E1B7 is part of the Major Environmental Unit E1.

The elevation of E1B7 ranges from 0 to 1747 metres above sea level, but 90% of its pixels fall above 21 and below 1042 metres. Its median elevation is 308 metres.

The Habitat Complex is higher in Dm5, elevation, rugosity and slope and lower in melt than the rest of Major Environmental Unit E1.

Comparison of environmental properties of this Habitat Complex with those of its Major Environmental Unit and the entire ice-free area of Antarctica

Biota

Most widely sampled species in E1B7 (found in most pixels)

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Xanthoria elegans</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Telosc histaes_Teloschistaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	46	3.14
<i>Rhizoplaca melanophthalma</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecan orales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	35	2.39
<i>Buellia frigida</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Telosc histaes_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	33	2.25
<i>Usnea sphacelata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecan orales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	33	2.25
<i>Bryum subrotundifolium</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Bryales__	Bryophyta	TRUE	31	2.11
<i>Umbilicaria decussata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Umbil icariales_Umbilicariaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	30	2.05
<i>Bryum pseudotriquetrum</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Bryales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	26	1.77
<i>Lecanora expectans</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecan orales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	25	1.71
<i>Caloplaca citrina</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Telosc histaes_Teloschistaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	24	1.64
<i>Lecanora physciella</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecan orales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	22	1.50

Distinctiveness of the unit from the Major Environmental Unit and the rest of Antarctica

Habitat Complex E1B8: *Large vertebrate aggregations*

These localised eutrophic terrestrial ecosystems occur near the ocean interface and receive massive nutrient subsidies from large concentrations of nesting or resting seabirds and pinnipeds that function as mobile links between land and sea (Otero et al. 2018; Bokhorst et al. 2019). The marine-derived subsidies and potentially massive physical disturbance to vegetation and soils distinguish these colonies from other coastal ecosystems (Gorta et al. 2022). Subsidies are greatest where the body size of colonial vertebrates is large (e.g. penguins) and breeding seasons are long. The habitat is most commonly characterised by large nesting colonies of Adelie, chinstrap and gentoo penguins, but large aggregations of southern elephant seals and Antarctic fur seals may also contribute significant nutrient subsidies. These animals select ice-free shorelines (mostly < 300m from coast) with gentle topography, low elevation (usually no more than a few metres above sea level), and high insolation. Nitrogen signatures and their biotic influence, however, may extend more than a kilometre from the nesting or aggregation sites (Bokhorst et al. 2019). Aggregation sites also tend to have high cloud cover, snowfall, and a long growing season even relative to other E1 habitats but may be exposed to prevailing winds. These sites may also be attractive to other nesting seabirds, including gulls, giant petrels, and the imperial shag,

among others. The large nutrient influx, primarily via guano and dung deposition, results in the highest terrestrial concentrations of nitrogen, phosphorus, and other nutrients on earth, as well as high concentrations of salt (Otero et al. 2018). This supports a unique trophic network of abundant mosses, lichens, algae, mites/springtails, other invertebrates, and extremely high microbial activity (Ellis 2005; Bokhorst et al. 2019). Surface disturbance by the large vertebrates is also a critical aspect of the ecology of these systems and largely prevents the development of large moss beds, which may develop some time after abandonment (Wasley et al. 2012) and within the enrichment halos beyond the immediate area of the colonies (Bokhorst et al. 2019).

Photographic images

Photo Credit: Steve Emslie. The Adélie penguin colony on Cape Adare, the largest rookery in Antarctica.

Chinstrap penguin colony

Distribution

Coastal outcrops all around the edge of the continent and Antarctic Peninsula, and on off shore islands

Environment

The Habitat Complex E1B8 is part of the Major Environmental Unit E1.

The elevation of E1B8 ranges from 0 to 1001 metres above sea level, but 90% of its pixels fall above 0 and below 170 metres. Its median elevation is 22 metres.

The Habitat Complex is higher in DDm5, cloud, meanTemp, totPrecip and wind and lower in elevation, rugosity and slope than the rest of Major Environmental Unit E1.

Comparison of environmental properties of this Habitat Complex with those of its Major Environmental Unit and the entire ice-free area of Antarctica

Biota

Most widely sampled species in E1B8 (found in most pixels)

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Pygoscelis antarctica</i>	Chordata_Aves_Sphenisciformes_Spheniscidae_Pygoscelis_antarctica	Chordata	TRUE	218	16.86
<i>Pygoscelis adeliae</i>	Chordata_Aves_Sphenisciformes_Spheniscidae_Pygoscelis_adeliae	Chordata	FALSE	201	15.55
<i>Pygoscelis papua</i>	Chordata_Aves_Sphenisciformes_Spheniscidae_Pygoscelis_papua	Chordata	FALSE	65	5.03
<i>Larus dominicanus</i>	Chordata_Aves_Charadriiformes__	Chordata	TRUE	26	2.01
<i>Macronectes giganteus</i>	Chordata_Aves_Procellariiformes__	Chordata	FALSE	25	1.93
<i>Leucocarbo atriceps</i>	Chordata_Aves_Suliformes__	Chordata	FALSE	17	1.31
<i>Bryum pseudotriquetrum</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Bryales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	12	0.93
<i>Cryptopygus antarcticus</i>	Arthropoda_Entognatha_Entomobryomorpha__	Arthropoda	TRUE	12	0.93
<i>Prasiola crispa</i>	Chlorophyta__	Chlorophyta	FALSE	12	0.93

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Polytrichastrum alpinum</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Polytrichales_ -	Bryophyta	FALSE	11	0.85
<i>Usnea antarctica</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae_	Ascomycota	FALSE	11	0.85

Distinctiveness of the unit from the Major Environmental Unit and the rest of Antarctica

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MAJOR ENVIRONMENTAL UNIT E2

Major Environmental Unit E2 is, on average, substantially higher in DDm5, cloud, meanTemp, melt and totPrecip than continental Antarctica. It is not substantially lower in any variables than the rest of the continent.

Major Environmental Unit E2 is, on average, substantially higher in suitability for Bacidiacid and Cladonid lichens, Polytrichales mosses, and Chinstrap and Gentoo penguins than continental Antarctica. It is not substantially lower in suitability for any functional groups than the rest of the continent.

Habitat Complex E2B1: *Snowy midland tundra*

Mainly occurring below 1200 m, this habitat may have gentle to quite steep slopes and typically has thick snow cover. Maritime influence makes conditions mild and cloudy with the highest total precipitation in the typology, but they are in windier locations, span a greater climatic range, have a longer growing season (degree-days above -5 degrees C), and occur on average at the lowest elevations in the environmental unit. The biota is characterised by common lichens, mosses and springtails, with some incidence of Antarctic hair grass (*Deschampsia antarctica*). This habitat has the most samples of hundreds of species including mosses, lichens, nematodes, mites, and springtails, with over forty found in at least 3 distinct sites. It is also the most commonly sampled habitat for the only two vascular plants in Antarctica.

Photographic images

Distribution

Occurs mainly along the western/southwestern coast of the northern and central Antarctic Peninsula, with scattered occurrences in Marie Byrd Land, Victoria Land and in the Transantarctic Mountains.

Environment

The Habitat Complex E2B1 is part of the Major Environmental Unit E2.

The elevation of E2B1 ranges from 0 to 4777 metres above sea level, but 90% of its pixels fall above 202 and below 1730 metres. Its median elevation is 814 metres.

The Habitat Complex is higher in DDm5, meanTemp, melt, rugosity, slope and totPrecip and lower in elevation than the rest of Major Environmental Unit E2.

Comparison of environmental properties of this Habitat Complex with those of its Major Environmental Unit and the entire ice-free area of Antarctica

Biota

Most widely sampled species in E2B1 (found in most pixels)

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Usnea sphacelata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	35	2.45
<i>Deschampsia antarctica</i>	Tracheophyta____	Tracheophyta	FALSE	28	1.96
<i>Pohlia nutans</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Bryales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	28	1.96
<i>Syntrichia princeps</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Pottiales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	26	1.82
<i>Polytrichastrum alpinum</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Polytrichales__ -	Bryophyta	FALSE	24	1.68
<i>Umbilicaria decussata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Umbilicariales_Umbilicariaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	23	1.61
<i>Sanionia uncinata</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Hypnales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	22	1.54
<i>Ceratodon purpureus</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Dicranales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	21	1.47
<i>Pohlia cruda</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Bryales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	21	1.47
<i>Usnea antarctica</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	21	1.47

Distinctiveness of the unit from the Major Environmental Unit and the rest of Antarctica

Habitat Complex E2B2: *Meltwater-eroded midland tundra*

Mainly occurring below 1700 m, this habitat encompasses a great variety of midland terrain types and is likely to exhibit seasonally thick snow cover. Relatively warm conditions and high snowfall are accompanied by especially high meltwater erosion, a long growing season, and slightly higher relief than average for the environmental unit. Meltwater erosion results in deep ridges/channels on the surfaces. A number of widespread moss species are accompanied by incidence of Antarctic hair grass and chinstrap penguin colonies. These systems are unsuitable for rotifers and algae.

Photographic images

Distribution

Occurs mainly along the eastern coast of the northern Antarctic Peninsula, though a few notable occurrences are found in the Transantarctic Mountains.

Environment

The Habitat Complex E2B2 is part of the Major Environmental Unit E2.

The elevation of E2B2 ranges from 0 to 4728 metres above sea level, but 90% of its pixels fall above 152 and below 3282 metres. Its median elevation is 929 metres.

The Habitat Complex is higher in DDm5, meanTemp, melt, rugosity, slope and totPrecip and lower in no variables than the rest of Major Environmental Unit E2.

Comparison of environmental properties of this Habitat Complex with those of its Major Environmental Unit and the entire ice-free area of Antarctica

Biota

Most widely sampled species in E2B2 (found in most pixels)

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Polytrichastrum alpinum</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Polytrichales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	18	2.03
<i>Sanionia uncinata</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Hypnales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	18	2.03
<i>Syntrichia princeps</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Pottiales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	18	2.03
<i>Andreaea regularis</i>	Bryophyta_Andreaeopsida_Andreaeales__	Bryophyta	TRUE	17	1.91
<i>Andreaea gainii</i>	Bryophyta_Andreaeopsida_Andreaeales__	Bryophyta	TRUE	15	1.69
<i>Bryum pseudotriquetrum</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Bryales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	15	1.69
<i>Schistidium antarctici</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Grimmiales__	Bryophyta	TRUE	13	1.46
<i>Usnea antarctica</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	13	1.46
<i>Ceratodon purpureus</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Dicranales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	12	1.35
<i>Andreaea depressinervis</i>	Bryophyta_Andreaeopsida_Andreaeales__	Bryophyta	TRUE	11	1.24

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Deschampsia antarctica</i>	Tracheophyta____	Tracheophyta	FALSE	11	1.24

Distinctiveness of the unit from the Major Environmental Unit and the rest of Antarctica

Habitat Complex E2B3: Cool dry midland inclines

Habitat characterised by relatively gentle terrain though it may encompass low ridges. On the southern Peninsula, it dominates low-relief nunataks and occurs in association with E4B2 where slopes are sunnier or steeper. Habitat is of midland elevations and the least steep and rugged in its unit. Its terrain reminiscent of E5 habitats, the habitat is dry relative to the rest of E2, receiving the lowest snowfall, cloud cover and meltwater in the unit. In some cases, temperature and moisture variables drop below the continental average. Sampled biota are dominated by lichens, but habitat suitability is lower than continental average for rotifers, algae, and certain lichen groups.

Photographic images

Distribution

Widespread in the southern Antarctic Peninsula, Ellsworth Mountains, and the Transantarctic Mountains, Enderby Land and Victoria Land, with a scattering in Marie Byrd Land.

Environment

The Habitat Complex E2B3 is part of the Major Environmental Unit E2.

Major Environmental Unit E2 is, on average, substantially higher in DDm5, cloud, meanTemp, melt, rugosity and totPrecip than continental Antarctica. It is substantially lower in no variables than the rest of the continent.

The elevation of E2B3 ranges from 17 to 4562 metres above sea level, but 90% of its pixels fall above 393 and below 2083 metres. Its median elevation is 1089 metres.

The Habitat Complex is higher in no variables and lower in DDm5, meanTemp, melt, rugosity, slope and totPrecip than the rest of Major Environmental Unit E2.

Comparison of environmental properties of this Habitat Complex with those of its Major Environmental Unit and the entire ice-free area of Antarctica

Biota

Most widely sampled species in E2B3 (found in most pixels)

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Pseudophebe minuscula</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	38	8.21
<i>Usnea sphacelata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	34	7.34
<i>Lecidea cf. cancriformis</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecideaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	18	3.89
<i>Umbilicaria decussata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Umbilicariales_Umbilicariaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	18	3.89
<i>Lecidea cancriformis</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecideaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	15	3.24
<i>Pleopsidium chlorophanum</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Acarosporales_Acarosporaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	15	3.24
<i>Acarospora gwynnii</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Acarosporales_Acarosporaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	14	3.02
<i>Rhizoplaca melanophthalma</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	11	2.38

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Carbonea vorticosa</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	8	1.73
<i>Buellia cf. frigida</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloschistales_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	7	1.51
<i>Buellia frigida</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloschistales_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	7	1.51
<i>Buellia pallida</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloschistales_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	7	1.51
<i>Xanthoria elegans</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloschistales_Teloschistaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	7	1.51

Major Environmental Unit E2 is, on average, substantially higher in suitability for lichens_Bacidiacid, lichens_Cladonid, mosses_Hypnales, mosses_Polytrichales, penguins_Chinstrap and penguins_Gentoo functional groups than continental Antarctica. It is substantially lower in suitability for no variables than the rest of the continent.

Habitat Complex E2B3 is higher in suitability for no variables and lower in suitability for no variables than the rest of Major Environmental Unit E2.

Distinctiveness of the unit from the Major Environmental Unit and the rest of Antarctica

Habitat Complex E2B4: *Inland meltwater-eroded mid-highland mountain slopes*

Terrain and elevation may be quite variable, but this habitat is characterised by high snowfall, cloud cover, and melt. Usually farther removed from the coast than most E2 units, it is more sheltered from maritime winds, lower in moisture (except E2B3), and higher in elevation than other habitats in environmental unit E2. Satellite imagery shows frequent deep lateral crevasses in adjacent glacier accumulation zones and rock falls where the unit is transitional between E4 units and the glacier below. Sampled biota includes mainly common lichens and occasional mosses. Suitability is low for most functional groups, but higher than the continental average of Bacidiacid, Cladonid, and Rhizocarpid lichens as well as most mosses and mites.

Photographic images

Distribution

Occurs mainly inland from the coast on the Antarctic Peninsula with a good representation in the Transantarctic Mountains and Victoria Land, again somewhat isolated from the coast.

Environment

The Habitat Complex E2B4 is part of the Major Environmental Unit E2.

The elevation of E2B4 ranges from 17 to 4482 metres above sea level, but 90% of its pixels fall above 693 and below 2816 metres. Its median elevation is 1433 metres.

The Habitat Complex is higher in elevation and lower in DDm5 and melt than the rest of Major Environmental Unit E2.

Comparison of environmental properties of this Habitat Complex with those of its Major Environmental Unit and the entire ice-free area of Antarctica

Biota

Most widely sampled species in E2B4 (found in most pixels)

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Pseudephebe minuscula</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	8	6.30
<i>Usnea sphacelata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	8	6.30
<i>Acarospora gwynnii</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Acarosporales_Acarosporaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	4	3.15
<i>Umbilicaria decussata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Umbilicariales_Umbilicariaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	4	3.15
<i>Buellia pallida</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloschistales_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	3	2.36
<i>Lecidea cf. cancriformis</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecideaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	3	2.36
<i>Pleopsidium chlorophanum</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Acarosporales_Acarosporaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	3	2.36
<i>Buellia frigida</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloschistales_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	2	1.57
<i>Ceratodon purpureus</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Dicranales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	2	1.57
<i>Lecanora physciella</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	2	1.57

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Lecanora polytropa</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	2	1.57
<i>Lecidea cancriformis</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecideaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	2	1.57
<i>Physcia caesia</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloschistales_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	2	1.57
<i>Pohlia nutans</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Bryales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	2	1.57
<i>Umbilicaria aprina</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Umbilicariales_Umbilicariaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	2	1.57

Distinctiveness of the unit from the Major Environmental Unit and the rest of Antarctica

MAJOR ENVIRONMENTAL UNIT E3

Major Environmental Unit E3 is, on average, generally higher in solar exposure than the rest of Antarctica. It is substantially lower in DDm5, rugosity and totPrecip than the rest of the continent.

Due to having a mid-range of conditions across the board, it is not substantially different in suitability for any taxa than the continental averages.

Habitat Complex E3B1: *Sunny exposed low-midland hillslopes/screes*

One of the sunniest habitats on the continent, this relatively mild north-facing ecosystem exhibits mainly medium but occasionally steeper craggy slopes and may be exposed to prevailing wind. It is primarily coastal except in Dronning Maud Land. It is relatively mild but the windiest habitat in E3. In Dronning Maud Land, this habitat often occurs alternating with E4B1 or E5B6 (depending on elevation and ruggedness) where light conditions are variable due to topography and aspect for all 3 habitats, with E3B1 representing well-lit inclines and slopes. On the Peninsula, it may alternate similarly with lowland E1 habitats and is prominently free of snow in summer (see photos). Primary sampled biota are lichens and mosses. Suitability is higher than the rest of E3 for algae, Acarosporacid, Candelarid, and Lecanorid lichens, liverworts, Bryales mosses and slim springtails.

Photographic images

Ecosystem complex with E3B1 in Dronning Maud Land (Google Earth Pro)

E4B1 on north-facing slopes in the North-east Antarctic Peninsula (Google Earth Pro)

Ecosystem complex containing E3B1 on Alexander Island (Google Earth Pro)

Distribution

Concentrated in Dronning Maud Land, with minor occurrences on the Antarctic Peninsula and in North Victoria Land.

Environment

The Habitat Complex E3B1 is part of the Major Environmental Unit E3.

The elevation of E3B1 ranges from 24 to 2862 metres above sea level, but 90% of its pixels fall above 278 and below 1887 metres. Its median elevation is 1276 metres.

The Habitat Complex is higher in DDm5 and wind and lower in melt than the rest of Major Environmental Unit E3.

Comparison of environmental properties of this Habitat Complex with those of its Major Environmental Unit and the entire ice-free area of Antarctica

Biota

Most widely sampled species in E3B1 (found in most pixels)

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Physcia caesia</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Telosc histaes_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	7	2.81
<i>Rhizoplaca melanophthalma</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecan orales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	7	2.81
<i>Xanthoria elegans</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Telosc histaes_Teloschistaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	7	2.81
<i>Umbilicaria decussata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Umbil icariales_Umbilicariaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	6	2.41
<i>Acarospora gwynnii</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Acaro sporales_Acarosporaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	5	2.01
<i>Candelariella flava</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Cande lariales_Candelariaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	5	2.01
<i>Syntrichia princeps</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Pottiales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	5	2.01
<i>Syntrichia sarconeurum</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Pottiales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	5	2.01
<i>Xanthoria mawsonii</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Telosc histaes_Teloschistaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	5	2.01
<i>Pseudophebe minuscula</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecan orales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	4	1.61

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Umbilicaria aprina</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Umbilicariales_Umbilicariaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	4	1.61
<i>Usnea sphacelata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	4	1.61

Distinctiveness of the unit from the Major Environmental Unit and the rest of Antarctica

Habitat Complex E3B2: Sunny sheltered midland hillslopes/screes

Typically exhibiting medium to steep rocky slopes that are visibly eroded by meltwater channels, this mild low-midland habitat is often found in association with E2B1 on the Peninsula, with this habitat facing north with meltwater channels in evidence and E2B1 facing south with thick snow cover. The wettest (high snowfall, cloud, and melt) and warmest in E3, with the highest solar radiation. Terrain is similar to E3B1 but sheltered from the prevailing wind. Sampled biota are scarce but suitability is high for Bacidiacid and Cladonid lichens, most mosses, mites, and springtails. The sampled biota appears to be dominated by lichens.

Photographic images

Distribution

A relatively rare unit that is sprinkled across the Antarctic Peninsula, North Victoria Land, Dronning Maud Land and the Transantarctic Mountains.

Environment

The Habitat Complex E3B2 is part of the Major Environmental Unit E3.

The elevation of E3B2 ranges from 44 to 4193 metres above sea level, but 90% of its pixels fall above 356 and below 2390 metres. Its median elevation is 1045 metres.

The Habitat Complex is higher in DDm5, cloud, meanTemp, melt, rugosity, slope and totPrecip and lower in no variables than the rest of Major Environmental Unit E3.

Comparison of environmental properties of this Habitat Complex with those of its Major Environmental Unit and the entire ice-free area of Antarctica

Biota

Most widely sampled species in E3B2 (found in most pixels)

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Usnea sphacelata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	7	9.46
<i>Arthrorhaphis citrinella</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Not assigned_Arthrorhaphidaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	4	5.41
<i>Pseudophebe minuscula</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	4	5.41
<i>Umbilicaria decussata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Umbilicariales_Umbilicariaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	4	5.41
<i>Lecidea cf. cancriformis</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecideaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	3	4.05
<i>Rhizoplaca melanophthalma</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	3	4.05
<i>Xanthoria elegans</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloschistales_Teloschistaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	3	4.05
<i>Acarospora gwynnii</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Acarosporales_Acarosporaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	2	2.70
<i>Cryptopygus sverdrupi</i>	Arthropoda_Entognatha_Entomobryomorpha__	Arthropoda	TRUE	2	2.70
<i>Cystocoleus ebeneus</i>	Ascomycota_Dothideomycetes_Not assigned_Not assigned__	Ascomycota	FALSE	2	2.70

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Lecanora physciella</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	2	2.70
<i>Lepraria cacuminum</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Stereocaulaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	2	2.70
<i>Physcia caesia</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloschistales_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	2	2.70
<i>Pleopsidium chlorophanum</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Acarosporales_Acarosporaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	2	2.70
<i>Rhizocarpon sp.</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Not assigned_Rhizocarpaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	2	2.70

Distinctiveness of the unit from the Major Environmental Unit and the rest of Antarctica

Habitat Complex E3B3: *Freeze-thaw slopes*

Exhibiting mid- to steep-grade slopes, this unit is usually sheltered from prevailing wind. In the McMurdo Dry Valleys, large swathes of this unit are soil covered and exhibit glacial patterned ground due to freeze-thaw cycles. Sampled biota are common lichens (Parmeliaceae dominant) and mosses (Bryales). Suitability is generally low for most functional groups.

Photographic images

Glacial freeze-thaw patterned ground above Wright Valley in the McMurdo Dry Valleys (Google Earth Pro)

E3 Ecosystem complex in the Prince Charles Mountains

Distribution

Predominantly found in North and South Victoria land, with notable incidence in the Transantarctic Mountains and the southern Antarctic Peninsula.

Environment

The Habitat Complex E3B3 is part of the Major Environmental Unit E3.

The elevation of E3B3 ranges from 9 to 3697 metres above sea level, but 90% of its pixels fall above 528 and below 2364 metres. Its median elevation is 1363 metres.

The Habitat Complex is higher in totPrecip and lower in no variables than the rest of Major Environmental Unit E3.

Comparison of environmental properties of this Habitat Complex with those of its Major Environmental Unit and the entire ice-free area of Antarctica

Biota

Most widely sampled species in E3B3 (found in most pixels)

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Pseudephebe minuscula</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	10	4.46
<i>Usnea sphacelata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	10	4.46
<i>Bryum pseudotriquetrum</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Bryales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	8	3.57
<i>Xanthoria elegans</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloschistales_Teloschistaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	7	3.12
<i>Umbilicaria decussata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Umbilicariales_Umbilicariaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	6	2.68
<i>Physcia caesia</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloschistales_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	5	2.23
<i>Rhizoplaca melanophthalma</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	5	2.23
<i>Acarospora gwynnii</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Acarosporales_Acarosporaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	4	1.79
<i>Lecidea cf. cancriformis</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecideaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	4	1.79
<i>Pleopsidium chlorophanum</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Acarosporales_Acarosporaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	4	1.79

Distinctiveness of the unit from the Major Environmental Unit and the rest of Antarctica

Habitat Complex E3B4: Sunny dry mid-highland sheltered mountain slopes

Typically exhibiting smooth mid- to steep-grade slopes that may nonetheless hold some soil or screes, this habitat has low snowfall, but also the lowest solar radiation, lowest wind, lowest temperatures, and highest elevation in E3. This unit may also exhibit patterned ground due to freeze-thaw cycles. It is frequently found in association with E4B5 where topography and aspect result in varying light conditions. It is prominent on the north-facing mountain sides above the McMurdo Dry Valleys. Recorded biota are mainly lichens. Suitability is generally average or low for all functional groups.

Photographic images

Distribution

Predominantly found in North and South Victoria Land, with notable incidence in the Transantarctic Mountains, Dronning Maud Land, and the northern Antarctic Peninsula.

Environment

The Habitat Complex E3B4 is part of the Major Environmental Unit E3.

The elevation of E3B4 ranges from 15 to 4759 metres above sea level, but 90% of its pixels fall above 833 and below 2482 metres. Its median elevation is 1641 metres.

The Habitat Complex is higher in no variables and lower in DDm5, melt, totPrecip and wind than the rest of Major Environmental Unit E3.

Comparison of environmental properties of this Habitat Complex with those of its Major Environmental Unit and the entire ice-free area of Antarctica

Biota

Most widely sampled species in E3B4 (found in most pixels)

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Pseudephebe minuscula</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	6	6.19
<i>Usnea sphacelata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	6	6.19
<i>Lecidea cancriformis</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecideaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	4	4.12
<i>Buellia pallida</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloscistales_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	3	3.09
<i>Pohlia nutans</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Bryales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	3	3.09
<i>Carbonea vorticosa</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	2	2.06
<i>Eupodes tottanfjella</i>	Arthropoda_Arachnida_Trombidiformes__	Arthropoda	TRUE	2	2.06
<i>Lecanora polytropa</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	2	2.06
<i>Lecidea blackburni</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecideaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	2	2.06
<i>Nanorchestes bifurcatus</i>	Arthropoda_Arachnida_Sarcoptiformes__	Arthropoda	TRUE	2	2.06

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Pleopsidium chlorophanum</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Acarosporales_Acarosporaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	2	2.06
<i>Prasiola crispa</i>	Chlorophyta____	Chlorophyta	FALSE	2	2.06
<i>Pygoscelis antarctica</i>	Chordata_Aves_Sphenisciformes_Spheniscidae_Pygoscelis_antarctica	Chordata	TRUE	2	2.06
<i>Rhizoplaca melanophthalma</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	2	2.06
<i>Sarconeurum glaciale</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Pottiales__	Bryophyta	TRUE	2	2.06
<i>Tetramelas papillatus</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloschistales_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	2	2.06
<i>Xanthoria elegans</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloschistales_Teloschistaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	2	2.06

Distinctiveness of the unit from the Major Environmental Unit and the rest of Antarctica

Habitat Complex E3B5: *Sunny mid-highland arid exposed nunatak faces and mountain slopes*

Typically exhibiting mid- to steep-grade slopes, this habitat is otherwise similar in terrain to E3B3 (e.g. smoother surfaces with little evidence of meltwater erosion). It is often found in complexes with other E3 habitats. This habitat is the least cloudy and driest habitat in E3 and has the gentlest relief along with E3B1. Scarce samples are dominated by Arthropods (mites, springtails) and Nematodes, but also contain common lichens.

Photographic images

Ecosystem complex with E3B5 above Lake Vida, McMurdo Dry Valleys (Google Earth Pro).

Distribution

Occurrences concentrated in the Prince Charles Mountains (this is the most common E3 unit here), Dronning Maud Land, and Victoria Land. There are minor occurrences in the Transantarctic Mountains and on the Antarctic Peninsula.

Environment

The Habitat Complex E3B5 is part of the Major Environmental Unit E3.

The elevation of E3B5 ranges from 51 to 4107 metres above sea level, but 90% of its pixels fall above 656 and below 2531 metres. Its median elevation is 1303 metres.

The Habitat Complex is higher in no variables and lower in DDm5, melt and totPrecip than the rest of Major Environmental Unit E3.

Comparison of environmental properties of this Habitat Complex with those of its Major Environmental Unit and the entire ice-free area of Antarctica

Biota

Most widely sampled species in E3B5 (found in most pixels)

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Gomphiocephalus hodgsoni</i>	Arthropoda_Entognatha_Poduromorph	Arthropoda	TRUE	7	10.77
<i>Eudorylaimus antarcticus</i>	Nematoda____	Nematoda	TRUE	3	4.62
<i>Nanorchestes antarcticus</i>	Arthropoda_Arachnida_Sarcoptiform	Arthropoda	TRUE	3	4.62
<i>Acarospora gwynnii</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Acaro	Ascomycota	TRUE	2	3.08
<i>Anurophorus subpolaris</i>	Arthropoda_Entognatha_Entomobryo	Arthropoda	TRUE	2	3.08
<i>Candelariella flava</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Cande	Ascomycota	TRUE	2	3.08
<i>Friesea grisea</i>	Arthropoda_Entognatha_Poduromorph	Arthropoda	FALSE	2	3.08
<i>Scottnema lindsayae</i>	Nematoda____	Nematoda	TRUE	2	3.08
<i>Stereotydeus mollis</i>	Arthropoda_Arachnida_Trombidifor	Arthropoda	TRUE	2	3.08
<i>Umbilicaria aprina</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Umbil	Ascomycota	FALSE	2	3.08

Distinctiveness of the unit from the Major Environmental Unit and the rest of Antarctica

MAJOR ENVIRONMENTAL UNIT E4

Major Environmental Unit E4 is, on average, substantially higher in elevation, rugosity, and slope than the rest of Antarctica. It is substantially lower in DDm5, melt and totPrecip than the rest of the continent.

This unit tends to be slightly lower than the average suitability across the rest of Antarctica for all functional groups of taxa.

Habitat Complex E4B1: *Exposed midland escarpments*

Characterised by steep, shadowed slopes, this habitat may be found in close association with sunlit E3 habitats where light conditions vary due to aspect. Habitat is the lowest elevation, warmest and windiest habitat in E4 (which is the steepest and shadiest unit), occurring where lower elevation or coastal mountains have sharp, high escarpments. Suitability is higher than usual for E4 for nearly all functional groups but still below continental average in most cases, excepting some lichen groups and Algae. Its sampled biota include several species of arthropods and lichens, most of which are found in more abundance elsewhere, though a few unique singletons have been documented.

Photographic images

Distribution

Very common habitat that occurs all around Antarctica, with concentrations in South Victoria Land, Dronning Maud Land, the Ellsworth Mountains and the Transantarctic Mountains. It appears in nearly every ACBR.

Environment

The Habitat Complex E4B1 is part of the Major Environmental Unit E4.

The elevation of E4B1 ranges from 0 to 3705 metres above sea level, but 90% of its pixels fall above 449 and below 2002 metres. Its median elevation is 1065 metres.

The Habitat Complex is higher in Dm5 and wind and lower in elevation than the rest of Major Environmental Unit E4.

Comparison of environmental properties of this Habitat Complex with those of its Major Environmental Unit and the entire ice-free area of Antarctica

Biota

Most widely sampled species in E4B1 (found in most pixels)

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Xanthoria elegans</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Telosc histaes_Teloschistaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	10	4.74
<i>Phycia caesia</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Telosc histaes_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	5	2.37
<i>Pseudophebe minuscula</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecan orales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	5	2.37
<i>Umbilicaria decussata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Umbil icariales_Umbilicariaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	5	2.37
<i>Usnea sphacelata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecan orales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	5	2.37
<i>Candelariella flava</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Cande lariales_Candelariaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	4	1.90
<i>Lecidea cancriformis</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecan orales_Lecideaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	4	1.90
<i>Pleopsidium chlorophanum</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Acaro sporales_Acarosporaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	4	1.90
<i>Umbilicaria aprina</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Umbil icariales_Umbilicariaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	4	1.90
<i>Buellia frigida</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Telosc histaes_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	3	1.42

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Candelaria murrayi</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Candelariales_Candelariaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	3	1.42
<i>Gomphiocephalus hodgsoni</i>	Arthropoda_Entognatha_Poduroomorpha__	Arthropoda	TRUE	3	1.42
<i>Halozetes belgicae</i>	Arthropoda_Arachnida_Sarcoptiformes__	Arthropoda	TRUE	3	1.42
<i>Lecanora physciella</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	3	1.42
<i>Prasiola crispa</i>	Chlorophyta____	Chlorophyta	FALSE	3	1.42
<i>Rhizocarpon geographicum</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Not assigned_Rhizocarpaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	3	1.42
<i>Rhizoplaca melanophthalma</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	3	1.42
<i>Sarconeurum glaciale</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Pottiales__	Bryophyta	TRUE	3	1.42

Distinctiveness of the unit from the Major Environmental Unit and the rest of Antarctica

Habitat Complex E4B2: *Cloudy escarpments*

High, rugged escarpments with some water availability, high cloud cover and highest snowfall in the unit. Some instances of this very rare habitat on the Peninsula have a short growing season, whereas most of E4 has almost none. Sampled biota are nearly all singleton species of lichens.

Photographic images

Distribution

Patchy, rare occurrences in the southern Transantarctic Mountains, Ellsworth Mountains, and the Antarctic Peninsula.

Full + regional maps (minimum of 30 km² to be included in regional maps)

Environment

The Habitat Complex E4B2 is part of the Major Environmental Unit E4.

The elevation of E4B2 ranges from 0 to 4700 metres above sea level, but 90% of its pixels fall above 423 and below 3207 metres. Its median elevation is 2016 metres.

The Habitat Complex is higher in DDm5 and totPrecip and lower in no variables than the rest of Major Environmental Unit E4.

Comparison of environmental properties of this Habitat Complex with those of its Major Environmental Unit and the entire ice-free area of Antarctica

Biota

Most widely sampled species in E4B2 (found in most pixels)

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Pseudephebe minuscula</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	2	7.14
<i>Usnea sphacelata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	2	7.14
<i>Blastenia succinea</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloscistales_Teloschistaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Buellia chrysea</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloscistales_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Buellia dendritica</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloscistales_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Buellia pycnogonoides</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloscistales_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Buellia siplei</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloscistales_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Candelariella flava</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Candelariales_Candelariaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Carbonea vorticosa</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	1	3.57
<i>Catillaria arachnoidea</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Catillariaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	3.57

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Catillaria floccosa</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Catillariaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Cladonia pleurota</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Cladoniaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	1	3.57
<i>Cladonia sarmetosa</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Cladoniaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	1	3.57
<i>Cryptopygus sverdrupi</i>	Arthropoda_Entognatha_Entomobryomorpha__	Arthropoda	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Lecanora fuscobrunnea</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Lecanora lilacina</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Lecidea byrdii</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecideaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Lecidea ecorticata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecideaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Lecidea stancliffi</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecideaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Lecidella siplei</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Physcia caesia</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloschistales_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	1	3.57
<i>Rhizoplaca melanophthalma</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	1	3.57
<i>Rinodina olivaceobrunnea</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloschistales_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	1	3.57
<i>Schistidium antarctici</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Grimmiales__	Bryophyta	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Usnea antarctica</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	1	3.57
<i>Xanthoria elegans</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloschistales_Teloschistaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	1	3.57

Distinctiveness of the unit from the Major Environmental Unit and the rest of Antarctica

Habitat Complex E4B3: Sheltered dry highland escarpments

Surfaces in this habitat are usually quite steep, shadowed, and may be topped by sheer cliff, but sheltered from prevailing wind. May have some limited meltwater erosion. Sampling is nearly absent, with repeat samples only occurring in lichens, and suitability is low for nearly all functional groups, though it is above the unit average for Bacidiacid and Cladonid lichens and several mosses.

Photographic images

Distribution

Occurs mainly in the Transantarctic Mountains and Victoria Land, as well as the central and southern Antarctic Peninsula.

Environment

The Habitat Complex E4B3 is part of the Major Environmental Unit E4.

The elevation of E4B3 ranges from 44 to 4398 metres above sea level, but 90% of its pixels fall above 678 and below 2755 metres. Its median elevation is 1514 metres.

The Habitat Complex is higher in totPrecip and lower in DDm5 and wind than the rest of Major Environmental Unit E4.

Comparison of environmental properties of this Habitat Complex with those of its Major Environmental Unit and the entire ice-free area of Antarctica

Biota

Most widely sampled species in E4B3 (found in most pixels)

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Pleopsidium chlorophanum</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Acarosporales_Acarosporaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	5	3.88
<i>Umbilicaria decussata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Umbilicariales_Umbilicariaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	5	3.88
<i>Buellia frigida</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloschistales_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	4	3.10
<i>Lecidea cancriformis</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecideaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	4	3.10
<i>Usnea antarctica</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	4	3.10
<i>Xanthoria elegans</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloschistales_Teloschistaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	4	3.10
<i>Acarospora gwynnii</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Acarosporales_Acarosporaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	3	2.33
<i>Physcia caesia</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloschistales_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	3	2.33
<i>Pseudophebe minuscula</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	3	2.33
<i>Usnea sphacelata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	3	2.33

Distinctiveness of the unit from the Major Environmental Unit and the rest of Antarctica

Habitat Complex E4B4: Highland clear arid mountain slopes

Usually set well back from the coast and removed from maritime influence, this cold (mean temperatures typically below -25 degrees), arid habitat occurs mainly above 1500m and exhibits the lowest snowfall and cloud cover in its unit. Terrain may be moderate to quite steep. Sampled biota are scarce but include mostly lichens, nematodes, and a species of Antarctic springtail (*Gomphiocephalus hodgsoni*). Suitability is low for all functional groups.

Photographic images

from the escarpments above the McMurdo Dry Valleys (Google Earth Pro)

Distribution

Occurs mainly in Victoria Land, the Transantarctic Mountains and Dronning Maud Land. Prominent ecosystem in the escarpments above the McMurdo Dry Valleys, alternating with E3 habitats where aspect makes sunlight conditions variable. Some minor occurrence in the Prince Charles Mountains as well.

Environment

The Habitat Complex E4B4 is part of the Major Environmental Unit E4.

The elevation of E4B4 ranges from 286 to 4860 metres above sea level, but 90% of its pixels fall above 1035 and below 2936 metres. Its median elevation is 1864 metres.

The Habitat Complex is higher in no variables and lower in DDm5, melt and totPrecip than the rest of Major Environmental Unit E4.

Comparison of environmental properties of this Habitat Complex with those of its Major Environmental Unit and the entire ice-free area of Antarctica

Biota

Most widely sampled species in E4B4 (found in most pixels)

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Scottinema lindsayae</i>	Nematoda____	Nematoda	TRUE	4	6.90
<i>Acarospora gwynnii</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Acarosporales_Acarosporaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	3	5.17
<i>Eudorylaimus antarcticus</i>	Nematoda____	Nematoda	TRUE	3	5.17
<i>Buellia pallida</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloschistales_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	2	3.45
<i>Carbonea capsulata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	2	3.45
<i>Hemichloris antarctica</i>	Chlorophyta____	Chlorophyta	FALSE	2	3.45
<i>Heterococcus endolithicus</i>	Ochrophyta____	Ochrophyta	TRUE	2	3.45
<i>Lecanora fuscobrunnea</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	2	3.45
<i>Maudheimia wilsoni</i>	Arthropoda_Arachnida_Sarcoptiformes__	Arthropoda	TRUE	2	3.45
<i>Prasiola crispa</i>	Chlorophyta____	Chlorophyta	FALSE	2	3.45
<i>Trebouxia sp.</i>	Chlorophyta____	Chlorophyta	TRUE	2	3.45
<i>Xanthoria elegans</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloschistales_Teloschistaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	2	3.45

Distinctiveness of the unit from the Major Environmental Unit and the rest of Antarctica

Habitat Complex E4B5: Highland clear transitional mountain slopes

Habitat has relatively low elevation and gentlest topography in this rugged and high-elevation unit. Sampled biota contains several repeat incidences of nematodes, mites, and springtails in addition to common lichens and algae. The lichen *Carbonea capsolata* is most commonly sampled in this habitat.

Photographic images

Ecosystem complex including E4B5 in Enderby Land (Google Earth Pro)

(Google Earth Pro)

Distribution

Patchy occurrences distributed around the continent, with concentrations in the Prince Charles Mountains, Victoria Land, the Transantarctic and Ellsworth Mountains, and Enderby Land. Tends to occur in small patches that are interlocked with other habitats.

Environment

The Habitat Complex E4B5 is part of the Major Environmental Unit E4.

The elevation of E4B5 ranges from 0 to 3811 metres above sea level, but 90% of its pixels fall above 681 and below 2461 metres. Its median elevation is 1457 metres.

The Habitat Complex is higher in no variables and lower in DDm5, melt and totPrecip than the rest of Major Environmental Unit E4.

Comparison of environmental properties of this Habitat Complex with those of its Major Environmental Unit and the entire ice-free area of Antarctica

Biota

Most widely sampled species in E4B5 (found in most pixels)

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Scottnema lindsayae</i>	Nematoda____	Nematoda	TRUE	6	6.90
<i>Acarospora gwynnii</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Acarosporales_Acarosporaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	4	4.60
<i>Carbonea capsulata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	3	3.45
<i>Lecanora fuscobrunnea</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	3	3.45
<i>Nanorchestes antarcticus</i>	Arthropoda_Arachnida_Sarcoptiformes__	Arthropoda	TRUE	3	3.45
<i>Buellia pallida</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloschistales_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	2	2.30
<i>Eudorylaimus antarcticus</i>	Nematoda____	Nematoda	TRUE	2	2.30
<i>Lecidea cf. cancriformis</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecideaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	2	2.30
<i>Nostoc commune</i>	Cyanobacteria____	Cyanobacteria	TRUE	2	2.30
<i>Plectus murrayi</i>	Nematoda____	Nematoda	TRUE	2	2.30
<i>Prasiola crispa</i>	Chlorophyta____	Chlorophyta	FALSE	2	2.30

Distinctiveness of the unit from the Major Environmental Unit and the rest of Antarctica

Habitat Complex E4B6: *Highland sheltered escarpments*

Steepest, most rugged and on average coldest unit in E4, usually remote from the coast or occurring coastally adjacent to ice shelf. Sampled biota are rare, comprising all single samples including several species of mosses, lichens and tardigrades, most of which are found more commonly in other habitats.

Photographic images

Vinson Massif in the Ellsworth Mountains

Distribution

This is the most common habitat in the Transantarctic Mountains. There are patchy occurrences in Victoria Land and on the Antarctic Peninsula, particularly inland from permanent ice sheet. Though rare, this habitat represents E4 almost exclusively on Alexander Island. In the Ellsworth Mountains, this habitat covers ice-free areas of the Vinson Massif, Antarctica's tallest peak. In Dronning Maud Land, this habitat occurs on the peaks of steep nunataks, interlocking with the more common E4B4, which occur on more wind-exposed faces and therefore have less cloud cover.

Environment

The Habitat Complex E4B6 is part of the Major Environmental Unit E4.

The elevation of E4B6 ranges from 12 to 4733 metres above sea level, but 90% of its pixels fall above 701 and below 3176 metres. Its median elevation is 1927 metres.

The Habitat Complex is higher in elevation and melt and lower in no variables than the rest of Major Environmental Unit E4.

Comparison of environmental properties of this Habitat Complex with those of its Major Environmental Unit and the entire ice-free area of Antarctica

Biota

Most widely sampled species in E4B6 (found in most pixels)

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Pseudophebe minuscula</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	3	7.69
<i>Encalypta procera</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Pottiales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	2	5.13
<i>Lecidea cf. cancriformis</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecideaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	2	5.13
<i>Usnea sphacelata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	2	5.13
<i>Xanthoria elegans</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloscistales_Teloschistaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	2	5.13
<i>Acarospora gwynnii</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Acarosporales_Acarosporaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	2.56
<i>Botryococcus sp.</i>	Chlorophyta____	Chlorophyta	TRUE	1	2.56
<i>Bryoerythrophyllum recurvirostrum</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Pottiales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	1	2.56
<i>Bryum pseudotriquetrum</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Bryales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	1	2.56
<i>Candelariella hallettensis</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Candelariales_Candelariaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	2.56

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Dicranoweisia turpis</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Dicranales__	Bryophyta	TRUE	1	2.56
<i>Diphascon chilense langhovdensis</i>	Tardigrada__	Tardigrada	TRUE	1	2.56
<i>Diphascon schusteri</i>	Tardigrada__	Tardigrada	TRUE	1	2.56
<i>Distichium capillaceum</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Dicranales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	1	2.56
<i>Echiniscus pseudowendti</i>	Tardigrada__	Tardigrada	TRUE	1	2.56
<i>Echiniscus sp.</i>	Tardigrada__	Tardigrada	TRUE	1	2.56
<i>Eudorylaimus coniceps</i>	Nematoda__	Nematoda	TRUE	1	2.56
<i>Gomphiocephalus hodgsoni</i>	Arthropoda_Entognatha_Poduroomorpha__	Arthropoda	TRUE	1	2.56
<i>Macrobiotus blocki</i>	Tardigrada__	Tardigrada	TRUE	1	2.56
<i>Macrobiotus sp.</i>	Tardigrada__	Tardigrada	TRUE	1	2.56
<i>Plectus antarcticus</i>	Nematoda__	Nematoda	FALSE	1	2.56
<i>Plectus tolerans</i>	Nematoda__	Nematoda	TRUE	1	2.56
<i>Pohlia cruda</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Bryales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	1	2.56
<i>Polytrichum piliferum</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Polytrichales__ -	Bryophyta	FALSE	1	2.56
<i>Rhizocarpon adareense</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Not assigned_Rhizocarpaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	2.56
<i>Sarconeurum glaciale</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Pottiales__	Bryophyta	TRUE	1	2.56
<i>Schistidium antarctici</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Grimmiales__	Bryophyta	TRUE	1	2.56
<i>Stereotydeus mollis</i>	Arthropoda_Arachnida_Trombidiformes__	Arthropoda	TRUE	1	2.56
<i>Tetramelas papillatus</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloscistales_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	1	2.56
<i>Tortella alpicola</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Pottiales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	1	2.56

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Umbilicaria cf. cristata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Umbilicariales_Umbilicariaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	2.56
<i>Umbilicaria cf. krascheninnikovii</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Umbilicariales_Umbilicariaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	2.56
<i>Umbilicaria decussata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Umbilicariales_Umbilicariaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	1	2.56

Distinctiveness of the unit from the Major Environmental Unit and the rest of Antarctica

MAJOR ENVIRONMENTAL UNIT E5

Major Environmental Unit E5 is, on average, substantially higher in elevation and wind than the rest of Antarctica. It is substantially lower in DDm5, cloud, meanTemp, melt, rugosity, slope and totPrecip than the rest of the continent. It occurs distinctly far from the coastlines in most cases.

Major Environmental Unit E5 is, on average, lower in suitability for all functional groups than the rest of Antarctica. This is especially true for Bacidiacid and Cladonid lichens, Bryales, Hypnales, and Polytrichales mosses, and penguins.

Habitat Complex E5B1: *Windy high plains/flatlands*

This dry habitat generally occurs around the low-relief fringes of rugged nunataks, or as isolated rock outcrops rising slightly above the ice sheet. Often unprotected by terrain features, this unit is barren and the windiest unit in the typology. It often occurs in association with E5B4. Several species of lichens, algae, and cyanobacteria have been collected as singletons, but are found more commonly in other habitats.

Photographic images

Nunatak in Dronning Maud land surrounded by E5B1

Distribution

Relatively uncommon habitat that occurs mainly in the Transantarctic Mountains, Ellsworth Mountains, Dronning Maud Land, and the Prince Charles Mountains. Occurrences in other bioregions amount to less than 50 km² per region.

Environment

The Habitat Complex E5B1 is part of the Major Environmental Unit E5.

The elevation of E5B1 ranges from 59 to 3114 metres above sea level, but 90% of its pixels fall above 825 and below 1989 metres. Its median elevation is 1299 metres.

The Habitat Complex is higher in no variables and lower in DDm5, melt, rugosity and slope than the rest of Major Environmental Unit E5.

Comparison of environmental properties of this Habitat Complex with those of its Major Environmental Unit and the entire ice-free area of Antarctica

Biota

Most widely sampled species in E5B1 (found in most pixels)

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Acarospora gwynnii</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Acarosporales_Acarosporaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	7.69
<i>Chlamydomonas sp.</i>	Chlorophyta____	Chlorophyta	TRUE	1	7.69
<i>Chlorococcum sp./?</i>	Chlorophyta____	Chlorophyta	TRUE	1	7.69
<i>Cymbella helvetica</i>	Ochrophyta____	Ochrophyta	FALSE	1	7.69
<i>Gloeocapsa sp.</i>	Cyanobacteria____	Cyanobacteria	TRUE	1	7.69
<i>Lecidea cancriformis</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecideaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	7.69
<i>Luticola muticopsis</i>	Ochrophyta____	Ochrophyta	FALSE	1	7.69
<i>Luticola sp.</i>	Ochrophyta____	Ochrophyta	TRUE	1	7.69
<i>Phormidium autumnale</i>	Cyanobacteria____	Cyanobacteria	TRUE	1	7.69
<i>Pleopsidium chlorophanum</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Acarosporales_Acarosporaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	1	7.69
<i>Stichococcus bacillaris</i>	Chlorophyta____	Chlorophyta	FALSE	1	7.69

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Tetracystis cf. fissurata</i>	Chlorophyta____	Chlorophyta	TRUE	1	7.69
<i>Xanthoria elegans</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloschistales_Teloschistaceae_	Ascomycota	FALSE	1	7.69

Distinctiveness of the unit from the Major Environmental Unit and the rest of Antarctica

Habitat Complex E5B2: Exposed remote plateaus and nunatak fringes

This habitat is situated on an uncommon juxtaposition of abiotic conditions, where gentle highland terrain encounters modest water availability. Snowfall and cloud cover is relatively high compared to the unit despite remoteness from the coast, which may improve suitability for some species by increasing water availability. Primarily associated with windy, flat to rolling dry terrain at high elevations removed from maritime influence and may slope gently. Scarce samples are all singleton diatoms, though this may be a function of sampling patchiness. Suitability in this habitat is generally low for all taxa.

Photographic images

from South Victoria Land, inland of the McMurdo Dry Valleys

Distribution

Rare unit that occurs remote from the coast in the Ellsworth Mountains, Dronning Maud Land, Enderby Land, the Transantarctic Mountains, and Victoria Land.

Environment

The Habitat Complex E5B2 is part of the Major Environmental Unit E5.

Major Environmental Unit E5 is, on average, substantially higher in elevation and wind than continental Antarctica. It is substantially lower in DDm5, cloud, meanTemp, melt, rugosity, slope and totPrecip than the rest of the continent.

The elevation of E5B2 ranges from 574 to 3477 metres above sea level, but 90% of its pixels fall above 1264 and below 2579 metres. Its median elevation is 1835 metres.

The Habitat Complex is higher in cloud and totPrecip and lower in DDm5 and melt than the rest of Major Environmental Unit E5.

Comparison of environmental properties of this Habitat Complex with those of its Major Environmental Unit and the entire ice-free area of Antarctica

Biota

Most widely sampled species in E5B2 (found in most pixels)

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Achnanthes sp.</i>	Ochrophyta____	Ochrophyta	TRUE	1	14.29
<i>Aulacoseira sp.</i>	Ochrophyta____	Ochrophyta	TRUE	1	14.29
<i>Caloneis tenuis</i>	Ochrophyta____	Ochrophyta	FALSE	1	14.29
<i>Cyclotella ocellata</i>	Ochrophyta____	Ochrophyta	FALSE	1	14.29
<i>Fragilaria berolinensis</i>	Ochrophyta____	Ochrophyta	TRUE	1	14.29
<i>Fragilaria sp.</i>	Ochrophyta____	Ochrophyta	TRUE	1	14.29
<i>Pinnularia maior</i>	Ochrophyta____	Ochrophyta	FALSE	1	14.29

Major Environmental Unit E5 is, on average, substantially higher in suitability for no variables functional groups than continental Antarctica. It is substantially lower in suitability for lichens_Bacidiacid, lichens_Cladonid, mosses_Bryales, mosses_Hypnales, mosses_Polytrichales, penguins_Chinstrap and penguins_Gentoo than the rest of the continent.

Habitat Complex E5B2 is higher in suitability for no variables and lower in suitability for no variables than the rest of Major Environmental Unit E5.

Distinctiveness of the unit from the Major Environmental Unit and the rest of Antarctica

Habitat Complex E5B3: Exposed midland meltwater plateaus

Primarily associated with windy, flat to rolling terrain at a mid-range of elevations, sometimes near to the coast, and may be sloping gently. May include both the top of plateaus and the gentle slopes under any escarpments. Though this habitat is dry, it has the highest melt and lowest elevation in E5 and is likely to be eroded by limited seasonal meltwater flow, unlike the rest of its unit. Scarce sampled biota are mainly lichens with three or fewer samples. Suitability is below continental average for all functional groups, but substantially higher than the unit average for nearly all groups, particularly Bacidiacid lichens and all mosses.

Photographic images

Ecosystem complex of E5B3 and E4B1 in eastern Ellsworth Mountains (Google Earth Pro)

Distribution

Modest occurrences are found across the Transantarctic Mountains and Victoria Land, Prince Charles Mountains, Enderby Land, and the Ellsworth Mountains.

Environment

The Habitat Complex E5B3 is part of the Major Environmental Unit E5.

The elevation of E5B3 ranges from 29 to 4533 metres above sea level, but 90% of its pixels fall above 493 and below 2277 metres. Its median elevation is 1087 metres.

The Habitat Complex is higher in DDm5, melt and totPrecip and lower in elevation than the rest of Major Environmental Unit E5.

Comparison of environmental properties of this Habitat Complex with those of its Major Environmental Unit and the entire ice-free area of Antarctica

Biota

Most widely sampled species in E5B3 (found in most pixels)

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Acarospora gwynnii</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Acarosporales_Acarosporaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	3	10.71
<i>Buellia pallida</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloscistales_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	3	10.71
<i>Pleopsidium chlorophanum</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Acarosporales_Acarosporaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	3	10.71
<i>Carbonea vorticosa</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	2	7.14
<i>Lecidea cancriformis</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecideaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	2	7.14
<i>Bacidia harrissoni</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Ramalinaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Buellia foecunda</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloscistales_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Buellia frigida</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloscistales_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Buellia grisea</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloscistales_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	1	3.57
<i>Carbonea capsulata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	3.57

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Catillaria inconspicua</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Catillariaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Huea smaragdula</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloschistales_Teloschistaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Lecanora expectans</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Pseudephebe minuscula</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	1	3.57
<i>Rhizocarpon flavum</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Not assigned_Lecideaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Rhizocarpon geographicum</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Not assigned_Rhizocarpaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	1	3.57
<i>Stereotydeus mollis</i>	Arthropoda_Arachnida_Trombidiformes__	Arthropoda	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Toninia johnstonii</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Rhizocarcales_Catillariaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Usnea sphacelata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Xanthoria elegans</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloschistales_Teloschistaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	1	3.57

Distinctiveness of the unit from the Major Environmental Unit and the rest of Antarctica

Habitat Complex E5B4: Remote arid highland bowls

Primarily associated with flat or rolling terrain at higher elevations, this habitat is less windy than the rest of its unit, though still above average compared to the rest of the continent. It tends to occur in the wind shadow of surrounding escarpments or in bowls, sometimes fringing lakes or glaciers nestled in valleys which also diminishes total insolation somewhat. Though snowfall levels are generally low, this habitat may accumulate more blown or drifted snow than surrounding steeper habitats. Sampled biota are very rare, consisting mainly of singleton lichens, algae, and cyanobacteria, most of which are more abundant in other habitats. Suitability is generally low for all functional groups.

Photographic images

Ecosystem complex including E5B4 in Dronning Maud Land (Google Earth Pro)

Distribution

Predominantly occurs far from the coast in the Transantarctic Mountains, Ellsworth Mountains, and Dronning Maud Land, with modest occurrences sprinkled across the most inland ice-free areas of Victoria Land and the Prince Charles Mountains. This is the most common habitat in the Ellsworth Mountains (just under 20% of ice-free area).

Environment

The Habitat Complex E5B4 is part of the Major Environmental Unit E5.

The elevation of E5B4 ranges from 88 to 4836 metres above sea level, but 90% of its pixels fall above 779 and below 2590 metres. Its median elevation is 1705 metres.

The Habitat Complex is higher in no variables and lower in DDm5 and melt than the rest of Major Environmental Unit E5.

Comparison of environmental properties of this Habitat Complex with those of its Major Environmental Unit and the entire ice-free area of Antarctica

Biota

Most widely sampled species in E5B4 (found in most pixels)

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Rhizocarpon geographicum</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Not assigned_Rhizocarpaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	2	7.14
<i>Acarospora williamsii</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Acarosporales_Acarosporaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Binuclearia tectorum</i>	Chlorophyta____	Chlorophyta	FALSE	1	3.57
<i>Buellia pallida</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloscistales_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Carbonea capsulata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Chlorosphaera sp.</i>	Chlorophyta____	Chlorophyta	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Coelastrum astroideum</i>	Chlorophyta____	Chlorophyta	FALSE	1	3.57
<i>Crucigenia tetrapedia</i>	Chlorophyta____	Chlorophyta	FALSE	1	3.57
<i>Cymbella helvetica</i>	Ochrophyta____	Ochrophyta	FALSE	1	3.57
<i>Gloeocapsa magma</i>	Cyanobacteria____	Cyanobacteria	FALSE	1	3.57

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Gomphiocephalus hodgsoni</i>	Arthropoda_Entognatha_Poduroomorpha__	Arthropoda	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Hormidiopsis crenulata</i>	Chlorophyta__	Chlorophyta	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Kirchneriella obesa</i>	Chlorophyta__	Chlorophyta	FALSE	1	3.57
<i>Lecanora expectans</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Lecanora fuscobrunnea</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Nanorchestes antarcticus</i>	Arthropoda_Arachnida_Sarcoptiformes__	Arthropoda	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Nitzschia acicularis</i>	Ochrophyta__	Ochrophyta	FALSE	1	3.57
<i>Nostoc commune</i>	Cyanobacteria__	Cyanobacteria	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Oscillatoria amoena</i>	Cyanobacteria__	Cyanobacteria	FALSE	1	3.57
<i>Oscillatoria chlorina</i>	Cyanobacteria__	Cyanobacteria	FALSE	1	3.57
<i>Oscillatoria limnetica</i>	Cyanobacteria__	Cyanobacteria	FALSE	1	3.57
<i>Oscillatoria limosa</i>	Cyanobacteria__	Cyanobacteria	FALSE	1	3.57
<i>Oscillatoria tenuis</i>	Cyanobacteria__	Cyanobacteria	FALSE	1	3.57
<i>Prasiola crispa</i>	Chlorophyta__	Chlorophyta	FALSE	1	3.57
<i>Schizothrix calcicola</i>	Cyanobacteria__	Cyanobacteria	FALSE	1	3.57
<i>Stereotydeus mollis</i>	Arthropoda_Arachnida_Trombidiformes__	Arthropoda	TRUE	1	3.57
<i>Stichococcus bacillaris</i>	Chlorophyta__	Chlorophyta	FALSE	1	3.57

Distinctiveness of the unit from the Major Environmental Unit and the rest of Antarctica

Habitat Complex E5B5: Windy xeric plateaus and moraine fields

Primarily associated flat to undulating terrain at high elevations removed from maritime influence and exposed to strong winds. May include both the top surface of the plateau and the gentle slopes under any escarpments. It also includes many moraine fields left by receding edges of glaciers over time, which produces visually striking patterned terrain reflecting the various stages of glacier recession (see below). This habitat is closely associated with steep habitats in E4 and E3 which often surround it. It is the coldest habitat in the typology (mean annual Temp -30 degrees centigrade), and the clearest, and lowest snowfall habitat in E5. Several species of lichens and Ochrophytes have been sampled but all are singletons and are more abundant in other habitats. Suitability is lower than continental and unit average for all functional groups.

Photographic images

E5B5 in the Prince Charles Mountains (Google Earth Pro)

Distribution

Predominantly found in the Prince Charles Mountains, where it is the most common habitat. Significant incidence of this habitat also occur in the remote highlands of the Transantarctic Mountains and Victoria Land.

Environment

The Habitat Complex E5B5 is part of the Major Environmental Unit E5.

The elevation of E5B5 ranges from 570 to 3559 metres above sea level, but 90% of its pixels fall above 1166 and below 2437 metres. Its median elevation is 1813 metres.

The Habitat Complex is higher in no variables and lower in DDm5, melt and totPrecip than the rest of Major Environmental Unit E5.

Comparison of environmental properties of this Habitat Complex with those of its Major Environmental Unit and the entire ice-free area of Antarctica

Biota

Most widely sampled species in E5B5 (found in most pixels)

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Biatorella cerebriformis</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Biatorellaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	6.25
<i>Bryum subrotundifolium</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Bryales__	Bryophyta	TRUE	1	6.25
<i>Buellia frigida</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloscistales_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	6.25
<i>Buellia pallida</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloscistales_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	6.25
<i>Carbonea capsulata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	6.25
<i>Carbonea vorticosa</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	1	6.25
<i>Chaetoceros sp.</i>	Ochrophyta__	Ochrophyta	TRUE	1	6.25
<i>Lecanora fuscobrunnea</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	6.25
<i>Lecanora mawsoni</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	6.25
<i>Lecidea cancriiformis</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecideaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	6.25

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Nitzschia closterium</i>	Ochrophyta____	Ochrophyta	FALSE	1	6.25
<i>Pleopsidium chlorophanum</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Acarosporales_Acarosporaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	1	6.25
<i>Pseudophebe minuscula</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	1	6.25
<i>Rhizoplaca melanophthalma</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	1	6.25
<i>Stephanopyxis turris</i>	Ochrophyta____	Ochrophyta	FALSE	1	6.25
<i>Trachyneis aspera</i>	Ochrophyta____	Ochrophyta	FALSE	1	6.25

Distinctiveness of the unit from the Major Environmental Unit and the rest of Antarctica

Habitat Complex E5B6: *Windy highland moraine fields*

This habitat typically occurs at high elevations and is usually found tucked in basins and on the fringes of nunataks, particularly in Dronning Maud Land. It often skirts habitats from E4 and E3, which form the more rugged nunatak peaks. It has on average higher slope and rugosity than the rest of its unit, but still represents quite gentle terrain relative to adjacent peaks. Satellite imagery indicates patterned debris fields of parallel ridges left by receding glaciers. Scarce sampled biota includes mostly singleton lichens which are more abundant in other habitats. Suitability is lower than continental and unit average for all functional groups.

Photographic images

Vesthaugen Nunatak © René Robert/IPF

in South Victoria Land by Mike Willis

Distribution

Predominantly found in Dronning Maud Land, and the Transantarctic Mountains, with relatively minor occurrences in Victoria Land and the Prince Charles Mountains. This habitat is found interlocking with E5B6 in the remotest parts of the Transantarctic Mountains and South Victoria land where terrain and snowfall variables differ.

Environment

The Habitat Complex E5B6 is part of the Major Environmental Unit E5.

The elevation of E5B6 ranges from 10 to 4508 metres above sea level, but 90% of its pixels fall above 1162 and below 2664 metres. Its median elevation is 1985 metres.

The Habitat Complex is higher in DDm5, rugosity and slope and lower in melt than the rest of Major Environmental Unit E5.

Comparison of environmental properties of this Habitat Complex with those of its Major Environmental Unit and the entire ice-free area of Antarctica

Biota

Most widely sampled species in E5B6 (found in most pixels)

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Pleopsidium chlorophanum</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Acarosporales_Acarosporaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	3	13.04
<i>Coscinodon lawianus</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Grimmiales__	Bryophyta	TRUE	2	8.70
<i>Pseudophebe minuscula</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	2	8.70
<i>Umbilicaria decussata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Umbilicariales_Umbilicariaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	2	8.70
<i>Acarospora gwynnii</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Acarosporales_Acarosporaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	4.35
<i>Caloplaca citrina</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloschistales_Teloschistaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	4.35
<i>Carbonea cf. vorticosa</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecanoraceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	4.35
<i>Diphascon sanae</i>	Tardigrada____	Tardigrada	TRUE	1	4.35
<i>Grimmia grisea</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Grimmiales__	Bryophyta	TRUE	1	4.35
<i>Lecidea sp.</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Lecideaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	4.35

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Lepraria cacuminum</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Stereocaulaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	1	4.35
<i>Minibiotus stuckenbergi</i>	Tardigrada____	Tardigrada	TRUE	1	4.35
<i>Nanorchestes antarcticus</i>	Arthropoda_Arachnida_Sarcoptiformes__	Arthropoda	TRUE	1	4.35
<i>Pannaria hookeri</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Peltigerales_Pannariaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	1	4.35
<i>Tydeus erebus</i>	Arthropoda_Arachnida_Trombidiformes__	Arthropoda	TRUE	1	4.35
<i>Umbilicaria aprina</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Umbilicariales_Umbilicariaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	1	4.35
<i>Usnea sphacelata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	4.35
<i>Xanthoria elegans</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloschistales_Teloschistaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	1	4.35

Distinctiveness of the unit from the Major Environmental Unit and the rest of Antarctica

MAJOR ENVIRONMENTAL UNIT G

Major Environmental Unit G is, on average, substantially higher in totPrecip than the rest of Antarctica. It is substantially lower in elevation, rugosity and slope than the rest of the continent.

Major Environmental Unit G is, on average, substantially higher in suitability for Gentoo and Chinstrap penguins than continental Antarctica. It is not substantially lower in suitability for any taxa than the rest of the continent.

Habitat Complex G1: *Active Volcanoes*

Recent and ongoing volcanic activity associated with active volcanoes is a highly influential ecological driver of ecosystem processes and biota. Active volcanoes that erupted within the last 1,000 years occur only at three restricted sites in the McMurdo volcanic field in northern Victoria Land (Mt Erebus, Mt Melbourne and Mt Rittmann) and one on Deception Island (South Shetlands). Mt Erebus on Ross Island is currently erupting and is closely associated with Mt Terror and Mt Terra Nova, which have been dormant for 800,000 years, but are likely influenced by eruptions of Mt Erebus, and are thus included in Ecosystem

type G1. The most recent eruptions of Mt Melbourne and Mt Rittmann were in 1892+/-30 and 1252+/-2, respectively. The Deception Island volcano is less elevated and isolated from the others and last erupted in 1970. All four active volcanoes are characterized by elevated temperatures and ongoing gaseous emissions. Three other volcanoes (Mt Hampton, Mt Kauffman, and Mt Berlin) exhibit some evidence of ongoing geothermal activity, but their status as active or dormant is yet to be resolved (Herbold et al. 2014), and therefore these have not been included in the active volcanic group.

Active volcanoes are polyextremophilic environments. The key physical features of these ecosystems include geothermal heat and steep thermal gradients relative to the surrounding landscape; periodic disturbance by volcanic eruptions, ash deposition or lava flow; emission of volcanic aerosols that contribute to dispersion of microorganisms (Van Eaton et al. 2013) and enrichment of nutrient levels (Garcia-Lopez et al. 2022). These ecosystems also include fumaroles (ice towers) and associated ice caves that form around vents, collapsing and rebuilding over decadal time scales.

Photographic images

Active volcano, Mt Erebus on Ross Island, Antarctica. Credit: NSF/Josh Landis, employee 1999-2001 - *United States Antarctic Program - Antarctic Photo Library, Public Domain*, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=3678885>

Distribution

Northern Antarctic Peninsula and Victoria Land

Environment

Active volcanoes are part of the Major Environmental Unit G.

The elevation of G1 ranges from 0 to 3730 metres above sea level, but 90% of its pixels fall above 0 and below 2978 metres. Its median elevation is 889 metres.

The Habitat Complex is higher in DDm5, elevation, rugosity and slope and lower in melt and wind than the rest of Major Environmental Unit G.

Comparison of environmental properties of this Habitat Complex with those of its Major Environmental Unit and the entire ice-free area of Antarctica

Biota

Bryophytes and algae dominate the eukaryotic component of the biota and thrive in mild temperatures and high-nutrient substrates, but are absent where temperatures exceed 40°C due to geothermal heating. Lichens are restricted to cooler peripheral sites. The bryophytes, present as thin films or conspicuous hummocks, include mosses, *Campylopus pyriformis* and *Pohlia nutans*, and the liverwort, *Cephaloziella exiliflora* (Herbold et al. 2014). Green algae (Chlorophyta and Charophyta) are widespread, while yellow-green algae and diatoms (Heterokontophyta) have been observed only at Deception Island.

Heterotrophic eukaryotes, such as protozoa and fungi, are present, but generally in low numbers and possibly limited to specific microhabitats.

The prokaryotic biota includes thermophiles and some psychrophiles. Emissions from the volcanic vents promote microbes with sulphur, iron and carbon metabolism (Garcia-Lopez et al. 2022). Photoautotrophic cyanobacteria are well represented on volcanoes but exhibit strong local gradients in relation to temperature and pH, and there are far more species on Deception Island than the other active volcanoes (Herbold et al. 2014).

Temperature and pH gradients are important filters of community composition at local scales. Cyanobacteria, followed by algae, and moss, are assembled along gradients from hotter to cooler areas. Local geochemical gradients are also important determinants of microbial community composition, with anionic and cationic constituents each accounting for 25% of microbial compositional variation in ice adjacent to vents on Deception Island (Garcia-Lopez et al. 2022).

Diversity of all taxonomic groups is greater on the maritime Deception Island volcano than the three more elevated continental volcanoes. Differences in elevation, nutrient status, solar radiation, disturbance history, maritime influence and insularity potentially all contribute to the differences in diversity (Herbold et al. 2014). Garcia-Lopez et al. (2022)

found the following microbial groups to be common around Deception Island volcanic vents: major phyla were Actinobacteria (27%), Bacteroidetes (23%), Cyanobacteria (20%), and Proteobacteria (most commonly the classes Betaproteobacteria (8%) and Alphaproteobacteria (5%). Abundant genera found in adjacent ice include *Hymenobacter*, *Pontibacter*, *Frankia*, *Cyanobacterium* and *Symploca*, while *Salinibacterium*, *Flavobacterium* and *Singulisphaera* were distinctive for Antarctica.

Most widely sampled species in G1 (found in most pixels)

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Gomphiocephalus hodgsoni</i>	Arthropoda_Entognatha_Poduroomorpha__	Arthropoda	TRUE	28	1.80
<i>Usnea antarctica</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae__	Ascomycota	FALSE	22	1.41
<i>Schistidium antarctici</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Grimmiales__	Bryophyta	TRUE	21	1.35
<i>Ceratodon purpureus</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Dicranales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	20	1.28
<i>Stereotydeus mollis</i>	Arthropoda_Arachnida_Trombidiformes__	Arthropoda	TRUE	19	1.22
<i>Sarconeurum glaciale</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Pottiales__	Bryophyta	TRUE	17	1.09
<i>Syntrichia princeps</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Pottiales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	17	1.09
<i>Hennediella heimii</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Pottiales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	16	1.03
<i>Polytrichastrum alpinum</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Polytrichales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	16	1.03
<i>Bryum pseudotriquetrum</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Bryales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	15	0.96
<i>Didymodon brachyphyllus</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Pottiales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	15	0.96

Distinctiveness of the unit from the Major Environmental Unit and the rest of Antarctica

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Habitat Complex G2: *Dormant volcanoes*

Dormant volcanoes last erupted 1,000 - 100,000 years ago. The geophysical and biological legacies of those events are likely to persist to varying degrees, distinguishing these habitats from their surrounding landscapes. Their substrates are likely to retain high levels of nutrients. Gaseous emissions may or may not occur (Bargagli et al. 2004), but are

generally less abundant than those that characterize active volcanoes (G1). Dormant volcanoes may also function as glacial refugia for unique biota. Older inactive volcanoes, that last erupted more than 100,000 years ago, generally lack these features and were classified with non-volcanic ecosystem types. Examples of dormant volcanoes occur within Marie Byrd Land, Victoria Land and Enderby Land, including the Hudson Mountains, Mt. Berlin, Mt. Takahe, and Mt. Siple.

Photographic images

Mt Takahe. Credit - US Navy - <https://pubs.usgs.gov/pp/p1386b/p1386b.pdf> Satellite Image Atlas of Glaciers of the World: Antarctica, United States Geological Survey, Professional Paper 1386-B (1988), page B131, Figure 96., Public Domain, <https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?curid=43798>

Distribution

Marie Byrd Land, Ellsworth Land and South Victoria Land. This is the most common type of ice-free habitat in Ellsworth Land.

Environment

Dormant volcanoes are characterized by legacies of past eruptions, including elevated levels of nutrients and geothermal heat, creating and thermal gradients. These ecosystems generally lack active fumaroles (ice towers), and gaseous emissions are absent or more limited than active volcanoes.

Dormant volcanoes are part of the Major Environmental Unit G. The elevation of ice-free dormant volcanoes ranges from 0 to 3485 metres above sea level, but 90% of its pixels fall

above 91 and below 2749 metres. Its median elevation is 549 metres. Dormant volcanoes fall mainly in the E2 and E1 units before the overlay process.

The Habitat Complex is higher in melt and wind and lower in DDM5, rugosity and slope than the rest of Major Environmental Unit G.

Comparison of environmental properties of this Habitat Complex with those of its Major Environmental Unit and the entire ice-free area of Antarctica

Biota

The biota of dormant volcanoes is poorly studied but is likely to share some components with active volcanoes (G1). Photoautotrophic eukaryotes are likely to thrive on high nutrient substrates, with bryophytes dominating where substrate moisture levels or humidity are high. Unlike active volcanoes, extreme high temperatures are unlikely to be limiting. Prokaryotic communities are likely to be diverse. Chemoautotrophic bacteria are most likely to be abundant in dark microsites and where there are high residual levels of iron or sulfur in the substrate. Local geochemical gradients are likely influential on spatial organization of the community (Herbold et al. 2014).

Most widely sampled species on ice-free areas of dormant volcanoes (found in most pixels)

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Gomphiocephalus hodgsoni</i>	Arthropoda_Entognatha_Poduroomorpha__	Arthropoda	TRUE	2	33.33
<i>Nanorchestes antarcticus</i>	Arthropoda_Arachnida_Sarcoptiformes__	Arthropoda	TRUE	1	16.67
<i>Pygoscelis adeliae</i>	Chordata_Aves_Sphenisciformes_Spheniscidae_Pygoscelis_adeliae	Chordata	FALSE	1	16.67
<i>Stereotydeus mollis</i>	Arthropoda_Arachnida_Trombidiformes__	Arthropoda	TRUE	1	16.67

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Usnea sphacelata</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Lecanorales_Parmeliaceae_	Ascomycota	TRUE	1	16.67

Distinctiveness of the unit from the Major Environmental Unit and the rest of Antarctica

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Habitat Complex G3: *Radiogenic ecosystems*

Heating of base rocks and water can result from processes other than volcanism. Such heating is presently known only from one small area of Antarctica on the Broknes Peninsula in the Larsemann Hills, where Cambrian rocks are heated by radiogenic decay (Fraser et al. 2014). These ecosystems lack gaseous emissions and nutrient release that distinguish volcanic ecosystems (G1 and G2). They are also characterised by a more moderate range of temperatures than active volcanoes. Radiogenic decay within rocks sustains geothermal heating over hundreds of millions of years. During climate shifts to glacial maxima, this sustained heating is thought to buffer conditions locally, as ice cover advances across the broader landscape. Higher levels of biological diversity at geothermal sites than in non-geothermal sites support the notion that geothermal sites function as ice-free refuges for ice-sensitive biota. While patterns of nestedness with distance from geothermal sites suggest recolonization occurs by dispersal from the refuges during glacial retreat (Fraser et al. 2014).

Photographic images

Larsemann Hills Oasis. Credit: Yurii-A-Dvornikov

Distribution

Broknes Peninsula in the Larsemann Hills

Environment

Radiogenic ecosystems are restricted to geological substrates with rare minerals undergoing radiogenic decay. This maintains mild soil and rock temperatures. Mineral nutrients are derived only from gradual weathering and, unlike volcanic ecosystems, are not periodically replenished by eruptions or aerosol emissions.

The Habitat Complex G3 is part of the Major Environmental Unit G. The elevation of G3 ranges from sea level to 152 metres above sea level, but 90% of its pixels fall above 16 and below 134 metres. Its median elevation is 74 metres.

The Habitat Complex is higher in meanTemp and wind and lower in elevation, melt, rugosity, slope and totPrecip than the rest of Major Environmental Unit G.

Comparison of environmental properties of this Habitat Complex with those of its Major Environmental Unit and the entire ice-free area of Antarctica

Biota

The biota of radiogenic ecosystems is poorly studied but exhibits high richness of bryophytes and lichens relative to most non-geothermal sites (Fraser et al. 2014). A range of cold-sensitive species inhabit the surface and subsurface. It also supports a range of soil- and moss-dwelling invertebrates. Herbold et al. (2014) describe the major groups of microbes found in the substrate, including Cyanobacteria, Actinobacteria, Bacteroidetes and Proteobacteria.

Most widely sampled species in the Broknes Peninsula (found in most pixels)

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Bryum pseudotriquetrum</i>	Bryophyta_Bryopsida_Bryales__	Bryophyta	FALSE	9	8.18
<i>Lepadella patella</i>	Rotifera__	Rotifera	FALSE	8	7.27
<i>Notholca sp.</i>	Rotifera__	Rotifera	TRUE	8	7.27
<i>Isohypsibius sp.</i>	Tardigrada__	Tardigrada	TRUE	7	6.36
<i>Philodina sp. 2</i>	Rotifera__	Rotifera	TRUE	5	4.55
<i>Daphniopsis studeri</i>	Arthropoda_Branchiopoda_Anomopoda__	Arthropoda	TRUE	4	3.64
<i>Encentrum spatitium</i>	Rotifera__	Rotifera	TRUE	4	3.64
<i>Adineta grandis</i>	Rotifera__	Rotifera	TRUE	3	2.73
<i>Buellia frigida</i>	Ascomycota_Lecanoromycetes_Teloscistales_Physciaceae__	Ascomycota	TRUE	3	2.73

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Cephalodella sterea</i>	Rotifera____	Rotifera	TRUE	3	2.73
<i>Collotheca ornata</i>	Rotifera____	Rotifera	FALSE	3	2.73
<i>Epiphanes senta</i>	Rotifera____	Rotifera	FALSE	3	2.73

Distinctiveness of the unit from the Major Environmental Unit and the rest of Antarctica

References

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MAJOR ENVIRONMENTAL UNIT L

Habitat Complex L1: *Lakes*

Antarctica has a diverse range of lake types, including surface lakes, wetlands and seepages, supraglacial lakes, epishelf lakes, and subglacial lakes. Habitat Complex L is constrained to surface lakes, and wetlands and seepages are covered in E1B2 and E1B5. Surface lakes are generally situated in coastal areas, particularly those that are permanently ice free. They range from small ponds, to kettle lakes and large lake systems such as Radok Lake (20 km² and 346 m deep) in the Amery Oasis and Crooked Lake (>9 km² and over 150 m deep) in the Vestfold Hills (Laybourn-Parry and Wadham, 2014). At least six surface lake types have been identified which include: stable lakes on higher-altitude areas; coastal lakes; stable lakes in old moraines; small unstable lakes in young moraines; deep cirque lakes; and kettle lakes (Nedbalová et al. 2013). They occur where meltwater drainage pathways flow from snowfields, glaciers, the ice sheet and permafrost into basins or depressions (including on glaciers and ice sheets) and are often spatially isolated. Conditions range from frozen solid to their bases in winter to seasonally ice covered, losing surface ice cover for a few weeks to months in summer, with some lakes being ice free year-round due to their salinity. Ponds, kettle lakes and associated wetlands are found commonly in the McMurdo Dry Valleys and are also seasonally active and vary in size interannually. Coastal lakes can be very numerous in some areas, for example there are over 300 lakes and ponds in the Vestfold Hills (Laybourn-Parry and Wadham, 2014), hundreds of lakes in the Bunger Hills (Klokov et al. 1990) and 150 freshwater lakes and ponds in the Larsemann Hills (Gillieson et al. 1990).

The geochemistry of Antarctic lakes is principally driven by salinity, redox conditions and nutrient and organic carbon supply. Salinities vary from freshwater through to hypersaline basins where seawater from previous sea levels was trapped. Some saline lakes are permanently stratified or meromictic, with strong physical and chemical gradients between upper mixed layers and lower unmixed layers. Dissolved oxygen conditions range from fully oxic to anoxic, with surface waters and ice margins usually well oxygenated but dissolved oxygen declining with depth, due to oxygen consumption by microbial respiration exceeding atmospheric diffusion or phototrophic production. The majority of lakes in Antarctica are oligotrophic or ultra-oligotrophic. Catchments of bare rock in continental regions provide little nutrient input, but in the Maritime Antarctic where there are vegetated catchments, inputs of carbon, nitrogen and phosphorous occur. Higher nutrient levels and eutrophication can occur in some areas due to inputs of faecal material from penguins or seals.

Lakes and wetlands support biodiversity and contribute carbon to surrounding soils. Antarctic lake biota includes benthic and planktonic communities. Plankton communities are usually dominated by prokaryotic and eukaryotic microorganisms, including Archaea, Bacteria, Algae, Protozoa, and viruses. The benthos is often dominated by cyanobacterial mats but can include mosses in some areas. Metazoans are usually sparse but include crustaceans (copepods, cladocerans and anostracans), nematodes, tardigrades, oligochaetes, chironomid larvae and tubellarians.

Photographic images

Lakes in the Vestfold Hills

Photo credit: Hassan Basagic. Lake Vida, Victoria Valley (McMurdo Dry Valleys)

Google Earth Pro snapshot; kettle lakes in the Dry Valleys

Distribution

Current knowledge about the distribution of Antarctic lakes is incomplete; however, over 1,300 terrestrial lakes have been mapped in ice-free areas. About 200 lakes have been documented in the northern Antarctic Peninsula, mainly on Deception Island and James Ross Island. Hundreds of lakes ranging from a few metres to a few kilometres across are dotted across the McMurdo Dry Valleys and extend down into North Victoria Land. Lakes are also documented in Marie Byrd Land, Dronning Maud Land, Enderby Land, the Prince Charles Mountains, East Antarctica, and the Transantarctic Mountains. Some areas, such as the Vestfold Hills and the Larsemann Hills, have notably high concentrations of lakes of various sizes, containing hundreds of lakes across a relatively small area.

Environment

The Habitat Complex L1 is part of the Major Environmental Unit L, but here it is compared to Unit E1.

Major Environmental Unit E1 is, on average, substantially higher in DDm5, meanTemp and melt than continental Antarctica. It is substantially lower in elevation, rugosity, slope and totPrecip than the rest of the continent.

The elevation of lakes range from 0 to 1960 metres above sea level, but 90% of its pixels fall above 0 and below 821 metres. Its median elevation is 120 metres.

The Habitat Complex is higher in no variables and lower in DDm5, elevation, melt, rugosity, slope and totPrecip than the rest of Major Environmental Unit E1.

Comparison of environmental properties of this Habitat Complex with those of its Major Environmental Unit and the entire ice-free area of Antarctica

Biota

Most widely sampled species in E1 (found in most pixels)

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Notholca sp.</i>	Rotifera____	Rotifera	TRUE	11	3.29
<i>Daphniopsis studeri</i>	Arthropoda_Branchiopoda_Anomopoda__	Arthropoda	TRUE	10	2.99
<i>Lepadella patella</i>	Rotifera____	Rotifera	FALSE	10	2.99
<i>Scottinema lindsayae</i>	Nematoda____	Nematoda	TRUE	10	2.99
<i>Ptygura crystallina</i>	Rotifera____	Rotifera	FALSE	8	2.40

scientific name	functional group	phylum	Antarctic specialist	count	percent of samp
<i>Diacyclops mirnyi</i>	Arthropoda_Maxillopoda_Cyclopoida_ —	Arthropoda	TRUE	7	2.10
<i>Encentrum mustela</i>	Rotifera____	Rotifera	FALSE	7	2.10
<i>Collotheca ornata</i>	Rotifera____	Rotifera	FALSE	6	1.80
<i>Eudorylaimus antarcticus</i>	Nematoda____	Nematoda	TRUE	6	1.80
<i>Philodina sp. 1</i>	Rotifera____	Rotifera	TRUE	6	1.80

Major Environmental Unit E1 is, on average, substantially higher in suitability for lichens_Bacidiacid, lichens_Candelarid, lichens_Cladonid, mites_Mesostigmata, mites_Trombidiformes, mosses_Bryales, mosses_Dicranales, mosses_Hypnales, mosses_Polytrichales, penguins_Chinstrap and penguins_Gentoo functional groups than continental Antarctica. It is substantially lower in suitability for no variables than the rest of the continent.

Habitat Complex L1 is higher in suitability for no variables and lower in suitability for no variables than the rest of Major Environmental Unit E1.

Distinctiveness of the unit from the Major Environmental Unit and the rest of Antarctica

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Bioregional Ecosystem Types

Bioregional Ecosystem Types (BETs) provide the most detailed estimates of biodiversity distribution in the Antarctic ice-free typology. They align with Level 4 of the IUCN Global Ecosystem Typology (Keith et al. 2022) and are appropriate assessment units for IUCN Red Lists of Ecosystems (Keith et al. 2013; IUCN 2024).

BETs were generated by intersecting the first two tiers of the typology with the Antarctic Conservation Biogeographical Regions (ACBRs), resulting in 398 candidate units, including 29 combinations comprising special ecosystems (i.e., geothermal areas, lakes, and penguin colonies). A number of these candidate combinations had very restricted spatial expression, some limited to a single pixel. While some of these may represent unique ecosystem types, we assumed this was unlikely if similar ecosystems occur in close proximity. Thus, excluding specialized ecosystem types, we lumped very small candidate units according to decision rules specified in Fig. below to resolve potentially articular fragments from the intersection process.

Figure S3-1 (from Tóth et al. 2024). Decision rules for lumping candidate bioregional units into the final BETs. At least 5% of pixels in the candidate unit under evaluation need to be next to a pixel of another unit to be considered “adjacent”.

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